

MEDINA

Deliverable D5.1

MEDINA requirements, Detailed architecture, DevOps infrastructure and CI/CD and verification strategy

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Abstract:	<p>This deliverable has a threefold goal. Firstly, it will contain the requirements of the MEDINA framework in close collaboration with Task 6.1.</p> <p>Secondly, the MEDINA architecture: its components, modules and interfaces.</p> <p>Thirdly, it details the DevOps infrastructure, namely the set of tools and services to support the continuous integration and deployment phases, as well as the CI/CD strategy to be followed for the integration of the MEDINA Framework.</p>
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Terms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CAB	Conformance Assessment Body
CISO	Chief Information Security Officer
CISQ	Consortium for Information & Software Quality
CSA or EU CSA	EU Cybersecurity Act
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
CVS	Concurrent Versioning System
CWE	Common Weakness Enumeration
DevOps	Development and Operations
DoA	Description of Action
DSL	Domain Specific Language
EC	European Commission
EUCS	European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
ICI	Internal Control Implementer
ICO	Internal Control Owner
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OS	Open Source
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
SaaS	Software as a Service
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
TOM	Technical and Organizational Measure
VM	Virtual Machine

Executive Summary

The final version of this deliverable, D5.1, is the first result of WP5, delivered in M12. Its main goal is to be a comprehensive document containing the general definition of the MEDINA Framework, the development methodology to be followed in the project and the infrastructure employed to construct the solution. This document contributes to the following purposes of the work package:

- To design the overall architecture of the MEDINA framework
- To set up the DevOps and SecDevOps integration environment
- To define the Continuous Integration and Deployment (CI/CD) strategy of MEDINA

The final aim of these tasks is to provide the basis for the main outcome of the WP5: the MEDINA Integrated framework, consisting of the integration of KR1 – KR5, which is to be reported in D5.3, the other main deliverable of the WP5.

The elicitation of requirements will directly interact with the technical working packages WP2, WP3, WP4 — in charge of developing the real components of the framework — and with the WP6 — in charge of defining the Use cases and the evaluation methodology.

The document starts explaining the methodology for requirement elicitation, that combines a top-down and a bottom-up approach. In the first case high-level requirements—that is, what MEDINA aims to offer—are elicited from what is written in the Description of Action and further detailed based on technical discussions. In the second case, each Use Case (developed in the context of WP6) has proposed functionalities for the MEDINA framework, so that the features offered can cover their needs.

The two Use Cases defined in MEDINA are presented briefly, along with the list of requirements derived from them, that have been defined in the WP6 that deals with the Use Cases. Then, the functional requirements defined in this WP, WP5 are presented and described in detail. An initial set of 77 requirements are presented, being 65 functional requirements and 12 non-functional. On the basis of these two requirement lists, an analysis of the relations and dependencies among the different requirement types, the Key Results and the components of the architecture has been worked out. As part of the analysis, different deployment models of the final solution have been presented.

Based on the requirements, the initial architecture of the MEDINA framework has been outlined. The architectural framework proposed by MEDINA can be abstracted in seven building blocks or well differentiated functionality groups (catalogues of TOMs/metrics/controls; NLP techniques/ontologies; risk assessment; certification lifecycle; organizational evidences; assessment of technical measures; evidence manager). These blocks are populated by a total of thirteen components, that are described using component cards.

To be able to develop the described MEDINA framework and components, a CI/CD strategy is employed. The Continuous Integration strategy to follow has been defined and described, that includes version control, regular check-ins and automated tests. The Continuous Delivery automates the release of the app into production, with no manual intervention. Additionally, some SecDevOps approaches are presented, to integrate the application and infrastructure security early in the development cycle. A containerized deployment model is foreseen to be used, based in Docker and virtual machines. Finally, to support all this strategy, a first benchmarking of tools has been performed, and a set of tools selected. Namely: GitLab CI, Maven, Jenkins, Artifactory and GitLab issues.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This deliverable is the result of WP5. Its main goal is to be a comprehensive document containing the general definition of the MEDINA Framework, the development methodology to be followed in the project and the infrastructure employed to construct the solution.

The document contains, first, the requirements of the MEDINA framework, gathered in close collaboration with the Task 6.1, that oversees the Use Cases definition. The methodology used for requirements management and documentation is also introduced. Functional and non-functional requirements of the MEDINA Framework are provided. The prioritization of requirements has a direct influence in the selection of the ones to include in the first release.

The description of the architecture of MEDINA form the second part of the document. That is, its components, modules, workflow and interfaces. The structural and behavioral description of the components conforming the MEDINA framework has been detailed. Each component is described using a template called “component card”, that includes the main information regarding the component as its functionalities, sub-components, interfaces, sequence diagrams or license, among others. Additionally, the data model of MEDINA is described, being the different entities categorized into seven groups depending on the building block they belong to.

The document also details the CI/CD strategy to be followed for the continuous integration of the MEDINA Framework. Also, the DevOps infrastructure to be used in the project is defined and described. It includes the set of tools and services needed to support a DevOps approach, and the different environments defined to support all continuous integration and deployment phases.

As the project progresses, the deliverable contents will be refined. This version is first release of the document. A second release of the deliverable is foreseen at the end of the second year of the project (M24), that will describe a more complete and refined system, and which will leverage the information received from the first implementation of the Use Cases as a feedback to update the design.

This deliverable is the result of Tasks 5.1 - Requirements, architecture and Infrastructure Specifications and 5.2 - Framework CI/CD strategy definition.

1.2 Document structure

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

Section 2 presents the methodology for requirement elicitation in MEDINA. It combines a top-down and a bottom-up approach to implement the requirements gathering process. Generic functionalities of the MEDINA framework to offer its value propositions from one side and what Use Cases expect from MEDINA components from the other side.

Section 3 describes the two Use Cases developed in MEDINA to validate and test the framework prototypes. How they are integrated in the actual systems used by Bosch and Fabasoft, what is the main objective of each UC, and the requirements are developed.

Section 4 describes the MEDINA framework requirements themselves. Requirements are primarily organized as functional vs non-functional requirements. A further division is made attending the module or component owning the requirement. Each requirement is uniquely identified by an id, that will be used to reference it in future tasks and documents, as the prioritization, validation, etc.

Section 5 presents the architecture of MEDINA. The components conforming the MEDINA framework are detailed, the workflow among them, the interfaces implemented and the used data model are described.

Section 6 details the CI/CD strategy to be followed for the continuous integration of the MEDINA Framework. Also, the DevOps infrastructure to be used in the project is defined and described, including the set of tools and services needed to support a DevOps approach, and the different environments defined to support CI/CD phases.

Finally, section 7 reports the conclusions.

2 Requirements management in MEDINA

2.1 Methodology for requirements elicitation

In MEDINA a combined top-down and bottom-up approach is followed to implement the requirements gathering process. Therefore the requirements are elicited in parallel in two strands: i) Generic functionalities of the MEDINA framework to present the functionalities MEDINA aims to offer as its value propositions, starting from the DoA [1] description and ii) Use Cases (UC) requirements for MEDINA. That is, what UCs expect from MEDINA components. Eventually, these two strands must merge.

Figure 1. Different requirements sources in MEDINA

The elicitation of the MEDINA Framework will be fed through several sources:

- **Requirements coming from the MEDINA action specification:** The first version of the requirements are elicited from the Description of Action by each responsible technical partner and detailed based on their knowledge and technical discussions held during the requirements description process.
- **Requirements coming from the Use Cases:** The Use Case will propose functionalities for the MEDINA FRAMEWORK, so that the features offered can cover their needs. This is done in the context of WP6.
- **Requirements from the technical providers.** The technical providers may provide new functional requirements based on the decisions made during the development of the design of the different tools, the definition of the workflow in MEDINA or the set-up of the MEDINA data model.

2.1.1 Requirements gathering and prioritization

This deliverable includes the first version of the functional and non-functional requirements for the MEDINA framework development and implementation. These requirements cover all the components to be implemented in the context of the technical WPs, namely WP2, WP3 and WP4. The requirements will be updated in the second version of this deliverable (D5.2).

Figure 2. Process followed in MEDINA for requirements gathering and prioritization

Legend for the next figure is as follows: Activities performed in this work package are marked in grey, while activities marked in green are performed in work package 6 (use cases validation).

The process followed in MEDINA for the elicitation of requirements is described as follows:

1. High-level requirements, that is, what MEDINA aims to offer, are elicited from what is written in the Description of Action. These requirements involve both functional and non-functional aspects that the MEDINA framework should provide.
2. This initial list of requirements is enriched with the understanding on how the workflow of information happens among the different components through the description of the MEDINA workflow (see details in section 5.1) which ends up with the definition of the MEDINA data model (see details in section 5.2).
3. The result of the activities described beforehand have been decomposed into functional and non-functional requirements
4. In parallel the Use Cases elicit their requirements for the MEDINA components. This is done in the context of WP6.
5. The technical partners then align the generic requirements elicited in previous steps with the requirements gathered by the use cases, and reformulated them, when needed, to end up with a consensus version.
6. Based on the final set of requirements (agreed in the previous step), both use cases and technical partners will prioritize them, taking into consideration not only use cases needs but also baseline requirements that affect other requirements, and in the event, it was not implemented, the related functionality would not be delivered in a successful manner.
7. The outcome of activity number 6 results in a prioritization matrix (Section 4.3.3 of the current document), that indicates for each release which requirements will be implemented and will therefore be able to be validated by the use cases.
8. Requirements will then be implemented into functionalities. The implementation includes the architectural design, the coding, testing (unit and integration) and deployment. During this phase, and especially during the testing activities, new requirements or improved requirements may arise. These new requirements are carefully analysed by the technical partners in order to avoid scope creep, before deciding if they can or cannot be accepted. If they are accepted, the functional requirements list will be updated.
9. Use cases validate the functionalities following the evaluation plan defined in D6.1 [2]. The evaluation can result in new requirements, as well as in updated versions of the current requirements. As in step 8, these new requirements are carefully analysed by

the technical partners in order to avoid scope creep, before deciding if they will or will not be accepted.

Furthermore, several traceability matrixes are maintained, to keep all the relationships affecting the requirements up to date. These matrixes are included in the section 4.3 of the current document.

2.1.2 Requirements documentation

Documenting requirements is a key issue in every software project. In the case of MEDINA, the requirements are defined to provide an understanding of what will MEDINA do, i.e. the functionalities.

For the prioritization of the requirements, from the point of view of the technological providers, the MoSCoW method [3] has been followed. The MoSCoW method allows to define clear priority levels while also determining which functionalities will be developed in each of the project iterations. The prioritization levels of MoSCOW can be defined as follows:

- **M (Must):** mandatory requirements. These requirements will be included definitely in the release.
- **S (Should):** requirements that should be included in the release or in the final version. The inclusion of these type of requirements must not affect the ‘must’ requirements and they will only be included in the case there is additional time of capacity.
- **C (Could):** requirements that could be included, because they provide nice-to-have functionalities. These shall only be implemented when the M and S have been successfully implemented.
- **W (Won’t have):** requirements that will not be included but they could be delivered some time as additional or extended functionalities.

Must and Should requirements are prioritized for the first versions of the components while Could requirements will be added in the final versions of the components.

In MEDINA, requirements are reported in a requirements document (this one) and are described as follows:

- **Requirement id:** unique identifier of the requirement
- **Short title:** short description of the requirement
- **Description:** more detailed description of the requirement. This is especially relevant for the creation of the test cases.
- **Status:** Proposed / Accepted / Rejected / Implemented / Work in Progress /Finished
- **Priority:** Must have / Could have / Won’t have
- **Related KR:** which MEDINA result is affected by this requirement
- **Reference:** Source of the requirement

3 MEDINA Use cases

This section gives an overview of the MEDINA use cases. The Use Cases have been described in detail in two successive versions of the deliverable *Use cases specification and evaluation methodology* [2] [4] in WP6. For a more elaborated information on Use Cases, please refer to the mentioned documents.

The first use case of the MEDINA project, provided by the partner Bosch, is focused on the EUCS certification scheme for high assurance [5]. It will be based on a multicloud deployment, leveraging three public cloud service providers: Microsoft Azure and Amazon Web Services—which is the architectural setup they currently use—and Fabasoft cloud.

The second use case is provided by the partner Fabasoft and builds around the real compliance activities regarding the Fabasoft Business Process Cloud.

3.1 UC1: European Certification of Multi-cloud backends for IoT solutions (Bosch)

Bosch business expands worldwide in four different market verticals (i.e. mobility solutions, industrial technology, energy & building technology, and consumer goods), which strongly depend on the consumption of public cloud services like Microsoft Azure or Amazon Web Services (AWS). Furthermore, Bosch has also become a provider of cloud services, which are mostly used as backends of connected products in the areas of mobility and consumer goods. Take for example the public cloud-based Bosch IoT Suite¹, which is the basis on which we build IoT solutions, services, and projects. At the time of writing, the Bosch IoT Suite connects more than ten million sensors, devices, and machines with their users and enterprise systems.

Given Bosch’s IoT context presented above, and provided the opportunity created by the new EUCS (European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services) for increasing citizens’ trust and transparency in connected services, it has become Bosch’s interest to consider achievement of the EUCS certification as part of our quality promise. It is our belief that EUCS, and more in general the EU Cybersecurity Act, will become a market differentiator for the kind connected services and products Bosch offers.

Central in the current EUCS draft [5] is the notion of levels of assurance (i.e. Basic, Substantial and High), which in consequence leverages the need for “continuous monitoring” and “automation” for a selected subset of high-assurance security requirements. The referred set of EUCS security requirements related to continuous monitoring is the starting point for the validation use case of Bosch.

The objectives of Bosch’s MEDINA validation use case are the following:

1. To pave the road for Bosch services considering achievement of EUCS High Assurance certification.
2. To experiment the implementation of a subset of EUCS security requirements associated to automated monitoring, on a real-world multi-cloud setup.
3. To provide relevant Bosch stakeholders with practical experience towards adopting the MEDINA framework for continuous certification.

3.1.1 Integration Approach

The validation use case of Bosch is focused on the challenges associated to the EUCS certification for high assurance. That means integrating the outcomes from WP2 – WP5 into the current AWS-

¹ Please refer to <https://bosch.io/iot-technology/>

Azure architectural setup presented in the previous section (including core services like Bosch CIAM), and including one additional public cloud service provider (e.g. Fabasoft) for the purposes of analyzing a complex cloud ecosystem.

The foreseen use case integration consists of two main approaches: (i) Technological integration and (ii) Process-related integration.

From a high-level perspective, the technological integration with the MEDINA framework will be incremental i.e. starting with Bosch services deployed on one cloud provider (e.g. Azure), and in subsequent stages integrating with those based in the other two cloud service providers (e.g. AWS and Fabasoft). An important requirement for Bosch’s validation approach in MEDINA relates to seamlessly integrating with their current IT security governance’s technologies. We refer to cloud-native technologies available for both Microsoft Azure and Amazon Web Services in the so-called “cloud security posture management (CSPM) [6]” field. CSPMs have been rapidly evolving and now allow cloud customers to perform automated compliance checks in their resources.

Figure 3. Bosch Cloud Deployments (after MEDINA)

But the integration approach will go beyond technology, as the proposed use case will also investigate adoption of MEDINA from the underlying security governance/certification processes’ perspective. Process-related integration and validation is considered essential in order to realize the effort of adopting EUCS with the MEDINA framework.

The main aspect of the process-related integration is the Bosch Enterprise IT Security Architecture (EISA) framework, where we will leverage the MEDINA’s framework in EISA components like TOMs, metrics and reference architectures. Expected outcomes include a mapping between EUCS and Bosch EISA, and an internal auditor’s guidance for continuous compliance of cloud security.

Also important for the proposed use case is the experimentation with EUCS’ “security profiles” (i.e. sector-specific security requirements applicable to market verticals like IoT), where refinement of existing Bosch’s security governance processes is expected based on results related to topics like composition of certifications.

3.2 UC2: European Cloud Service Provider SaaS public & private cloud (Fabasoft)

Fabasoft is a European software manufacturer and cloud provider. The software products and cloud services from Fabasoft ensure the consistent capture, sorting, process-oriented handling, secure storage and context-sensitive finding of all digital business documents. These functions are used in both on-premises installations, as well as in Software as a Service (SaaS) cloud solutions. Beyond that, the Fabasoft appliance concept offers a direct way to provide customers with standardized complete systems (hardware and software) for use in their own data processing centers.

Fabasoft is already compliant with the following relevant standards or certifications: ISO 9001; ISO 20000-1; ISO 27001 including ISO 27018 controls; BSI C5:2017 (C5:2020 audit is currently in progress); ISAE 3402 Type 2; ISAE 3000 SOC 2 Type 1

The motivation of Fabasoft to participate in MEDINA and to provide this use case is the business driver of cost efficiency behind the idea of a successful automated, continuous audit approach. Currently, an audit for a BSIC5:2020 attestation at Fabasoft follows the traditional conventions and splits into three phases: set-up, compliance-evaluation and re-evaluation.

1. **Set-up-Phase:** This phase is a one-time activity for each new compliance framework that Fabasoft applies for. The Compliance Manager—responsible for organizing the compliance process—has to select the applicable categories of the BSI C5:2020 framework. Together with a system description, this comprises the Statement of Applicability (SoA).

In a next step, the Compliance Manager delegates all Security Controls collected in the SoA internally to key-experts and -employees who are able to provide compliance-solutions for a sub-set Security Controls to meet their requirements and implement the evidence collection. These implementations are called Internal Controls and thus the responsible person for such a control is called Internal Control Owner (ICO).

The combination of SoA and implementation of Internal Controls is forwarded to the Auditor and assessed for a first feedback and starting point of the next phase.

2. **Compliance-Evaluation-Phase:** This phase is defined to be a one-time activity for each new Security Control Framework that Fabasoft applies for.

For a BSI C5:2020 attestation this phase follows an annual standard and evidences are collected over the course of 12 months for each Internal Control and then audited over the course of approximately 3 – 4 weeks between the Auditors, the Compliance Manager and all responsible ICOs to verify the correctness of the controls and the management of incidences, if they occurred.

3. **Re-Evaluation-Phase:** This phase is defined to be a yearly repetition of the Compliance-Evaluation-Phase. The difference is that it also involves verification and updates of controls in place and checks the correctness of responsibilities of ICOs. It is a plan-do-check-act cycle and culminates in a 3 – 4 weeks audit with all responsible persons every 12 months.

Problem Statement: By looking at the three describes phases, it becomes obvious that this is not only a costly undertaking with respect to the service costs of the auditing instance but also very resource intensive for a company like Fabasoft. For comparison, at early 2021, Fabasoft has had about 300 employees and involved nearly 12 people in a 4-week audit for BSI C5: 2020. These figures indicate a recurring high cost involvement for a CSP when it comes to this framework. Currently there is no reason to believe that this will be any different for the upcoming EUCS.

The ultimate goal for Fabasoft in this project is to achieve a framework that allows for an (almost) automated, continuous audit process when applying a scheme like BSI C5 or EUCS. To achieve that we expect MEDINA to offer methods and tools to analyze information either directly – via tools like Clouditor – or indirectly by being able to process output from their internal monitoring tools or currently active scripts we implemented for the traditional BSI C5 evidence collection. We also expect MEDINA to offer us tools and methods to fetch information about Security Controls from some kind of repository that are translated into a rule-based language so that an internal expert can implement the security measures necessary to comply to the rules stated in that Security Control. This is, offer a framework that is less prone to different interpretation for Security Controls and offers more clear instruction on what to report for each Security Controls to achieve compliance to a framework like EUCS.

3.2.1 Integration Approach and Expected Benefits (after MEDINA)

As mentioned, Fabasoft expects MEDINA to offer a strong increase in efficiency combined with a significant cost reduction in the long run, especially when it comes to multi-audits for different compliance frameworks. To achieve that and to test the MEDINA functionality, Fabasoft will set up a Demo-System in a Virtual Development Environment (VDE) which is a perfect virtual clone of the Fabasoft Cloud production environment. By doing this, both above mentioned scenarios can be achieved: the application of MEDINA in a private and a public cloud SaaS solution.²

Currently, there is no scenario where a CSP would simply install a MEDINA software framework into its own datacenters and let it “just work”. So, to make use of the MEDINA approach, Use Case 2 will tackle it as a framework that can be accessed via an audit API, illustrated as the green lines in Figure 4, which will enable a Compliance Manager at Fabasoft to communicate with the several components offered by MEDINA. MEDINA will not have direct access to the Fabasoft Cloud at all levels and each stack, but will “ask” for correct return values according to the configuration of an audit that the Compliance Manager will specify in the Fabasoft Certification App. The Audit API is also the point of connection for the auditor, who will have to validate the Fabasoft implementation for all Security Controls and the different implementations of the configured return values to the MEDINA Framework.

Figure 4. Illustration of Use Case 2 Demo-System

Note that the auditor does not directly interact with the Fabasoft system. We will design it this way, because we expect auditors to use a specific MEDINA UI to fulfill their tasks within an audit process. We strongly believe that if auditors would have to connect to each individual

² The VDE is applicable for the public Fabasoft Cloud and the on-premise installation, the private cloud.

implementation of a MEDINA audit functionality, the number of different systems an auditor has to deal with will create a huge overhead for them and thus is not feasible.

3.3 Use Cases requirement list

This chapter offers a list of the Use Cases requirements collected in WP6. As mentioned before, they are extracted from deliverable D6.2 [4], where a more detailed description can be found. For the sake of clarity, the table includes discarded requirements (in red color) with respect to previous version (D6.1 [2]) and new ones (green color). This list is not static and can change as the work progresses. The changes will be reflected in future version of the documents of WP6, and in the next version of this deliverable, D5.2, due at M24.

The requirements are divided in “Common Requirements”—those not directly related to one of the use cases or that might occur in both—and “Use Case Specific Requirements”—those only related to one use case and do not directly or indirectly apply to the other use case-.

Table 1. List of Use Case requirements

Type	Req. ID	Short Title
Common	UC00.01	MEDINA Audit API
	UC00.02	Repository of Security Controls
	UC00.03	Technical Coverage of BSI C5 Security Controls
	UC00.04	Secure Evidence Storage
	UC00.05	Evidence Mapping
	UC00.06	Security Controls Translator
	UC00.07	Define Measurement Targets
	UC00.08	Add Traditional Audit results to MEDINA results
	UC00.09	Request for Change on Assessment Rules
	UC00.10	Request for Change on Persona Ref. TOMs
	UC00.11	Assessment Results return value
	UC00.12	Risk Assessment import
	UC00.13	Auditor access to Assessment Results
	UC00.14	Compliance Status notification
	UC00.15	MEDINA Assessment Rules run-time change
	UC00.16	MEDINA Measurement Target run-time change
	UC00.17	MEDINA complies to EUCS
	UC00.18	MEDINA tool modularity
	UC00.19	Mapping of Frameworks
	UC00.20	Scalable Framework
	UC00.21	Interoperability API
	UC00.22	Data collection extent
	UC00.23	Retention of evidences
	UC00.24	Compliance Certification Status
	UC00.25	Efficiency Improvements (Automation)
	UC00.26	Efficiency Improvements
	UC00.27	Monitoring of Organizational Measures
	UC00.28	Report Generation
	UC00.29	Unified Graphical User Interface
	UC00.30	Internal Regulation Checks Support
	UC00.31	Trustworthiness of Evidences
	UC00.32	Attribution of Security Controls
UC1	UC01.1	Compliance Status Aggregation on Corporate Level

	UC01.2	Compliance Dashboard on Corporate Level
	UC01.3	Misconfiguration Monitoring on Corporate Level
	UC01.4	Non-compliance Monitoring on Corporate Level
	UC01.5	Aggregate Attribution of Non-Compliances
	UC01.6	Graphical User Interface
	UC01.7	Misconfiguration Tracking
	UC01.8	Identification of Individual Non-Compliant Resources
	UC01.9	Compliance Certification Status on Corporate Level
	UC01.10	Compliance Status Aggregation on Domain Level
	UC01.11	Compliance Status Aggregation on Domain Level
	UC01.12	Compliance Status Aggregation on Domain Level
	UC01.13	Aggregate Attribution of Non-Compliances on Domain Level
	UC01.14	Compliance Certification Status on Domain Level
	UC01.15	Misconfiguration Monitoring on Product Level
	UC01.16	Non-compliance Monitoring on Product Level
	UC01.17	Feedback on Remediation Actions
	UC01.18	Provision of Remediation Guidance
	UC01.19	Configuration
	UC01.20	Compliance Certification Status on Product Level
	UC01.21	Compliance and Certification Status in Product Composition
	UC01.22	Integration with Asset Management
	UC01.23	Framework Tools Setup and Configuration Automation
	UC01.24	User Interface Single Pane of Glass
	UC01.25	User Interface Time and Product Scope Adjustability
	UC01.26	Selectable Certification Schemes and Security Frameworks
	UC01.27	Selectable Controls in Compliance Dashboard
	UC01.28	Identification of Compliance Issues in Composed Products / Services
	UC01.29	Integration with Cloud-native Security Posture Management
	UC01.30	Interfaces for the Provision of Organizational Evidences
	UC01.31	Product-specific Customization of Certification Scheme
UC2	UC02.01	Dashboard for the Compliance Manager
	UC02.02	Delegation of compliance tasks from Compliance Manager to Internal Control Owner
	UC02.03	Set up of Internal Control by Compliance Manager
	UC02.04	Mapping of Internal Controls to Security Controls by Compliance Manager or ICO
	UC02.05	Application to the same Security Control Framework to different Subsidiaries or Projects of the Corporation
	UC02.06	Tracking of Internal Controls by Compliance Manager
	UC02.07	Comprisal of Implementation Report by Compliance Manager for Auditor
	UC02.08	Comprisal of Report by Compliance Manager
	UC02.09	Elimination of risk for non-compliance
	UC02.10	Sleek UI
	UC02.11	Verify correspondence of Internal Controls and Persona Ref. TOMS to Internal Control System Policy
	UC02.12	Accept or decline ownership of Security Control
	UC02.13	Change status of Internal Control

4 MEDINA Framework requirements

4.1 Functional requirements

4.1.1 Repository of controls, metrics, measures and necessary evidences

The repository of controls, metrics, measures and necessary evidences will be an IT tool for the storage and management of these elements and their relationships.

Requirement id	RCME.01
Short title	Catalogue of metrics, controls and TOMs
Description	<p>The repository shall contain a catalogue of elements (categories, TOMs and reference implementations, controls and controls objectives, assurance levels) associated to the security control frameworks (see RCME.02 for the list of frameworks to be included), including:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) clear definition of the categories of each security control framework included in the catalogue 2) clear definition of the security controls inside each category 3) clear definition of the TOMs (aka security requirements) for each control relevant for cloud service providers if relevant³. This definition shall contain guidance in the techniques and tools to be used for the evidence 4) clear definition of the assurance level corresponding to each security requirement if relevant 5) clear identification of evidences that would comply with the security controls and requirements 6) clear definition of the reference implementations of TOMs. These references implementations shall be selected by the CSP for each cloud service. 7) corresponding quantitative and qualitative metrics for each TOM 8) target values of the quantitative and qualitative metrics. These values shall be configurable by the CSP for each cloud service
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR 1
Reference	<p>DoA part B Annex 1 page 6 DoA part B Annex 1 page 7 DoA part B Annex 1 page 10 For point 4), technology provider</p>

Requirement id	RCME.02
Short title	Metrics and TOMs in the repository
Description	<p>The repository should include realizable metrics for at least for the 70% of the TOMs referenced in major security control frameworks related to system security and integrity, operational security, business continuity and incident management.</p> <p>These include: EUCS, ISO/IEC 27002. ISO/IEC 27017, ISO/IEC 27018, ANSII SecNumCloud, BSI C5 and the ENISA Metaframework.</p>
Status	Proposed

³ Not all security certification schemes have requirements defined. Some, such as BSI C5 and ISO 27001 remain at the level of security control.

Priority	Must
Related KR	KR 1
Reference	DoA part B Annex 1 page 7

Requirement id	RCME.03
Short title	Metrics and TOMs for different assurance levels
Description	The repository should include metrics for TOMs for basic (Y3), substantial (Y2) and high assurance levels(Y1)
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR 1
Reference	DoA part B Annex 1 page 7

Requirement id	RCME.04
Short title	Technology agnostic security controls
Description	The definition of the security controls in the repository should be technology agnostic, that is, they must be valid for a number of different implementations and cannot be technology specific.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR 1
Reference	DoA part B Annex 1 page 15

Requirement id	RCME.05
Short title	Interfaces to the continuous auditing tools
Description	The repository should be accessible by the continuous evaluation tools.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR 1
Reference	DoA part B Annex 1 page 15

Requirement id	RCME.06
Short title	Homogenization of the certification schemes
Description	The repository as part of the MEDINA framework should support the homogenization of certification schemes, by aligning to the EUCS. Thus, the repository must include information about the coverage of the different similar controls ⁴ in the different (national) schemes.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR 1
Reference	DoA part B Annex 1 page 31

⁴ In a preliminary comparative analysis of the security control frameworks it has been confirmed that the minimum level to compare the frameworks is the controls. See D2.1 for more detail [38].

4.1.2 Certification Language

4.1.2.1 NLCS translator (CNR)

Requirement id	NLCS.01
Short title	Translation from natural language to controlled natural language
Description	The tool shall be able to translate, in a semi-automatic translate (meaning, with little human intervention, the most relevant aspects of a security certification scheme – originally expressed in natural language (English), into a controlled natural language, which maintains a readability for non-experts users, but it can processable by machines.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	NLCS.02
Short title	Based on NLP and ontologies
Description	The tool will ground on NLP methodology to process single parts of the natural sentences in the cloud certification schemes and on ontologies representation to link the terms of the sentences with the terms of the chosen controlled natural language.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	NLCS.03
Short title	Translation of organizational measures and technical measures
Description	NLCS will be able to translate all the organizational measures specified in the chosen EU cloud certification schemas, and some of the technical measures.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	NLCS.04
Short title	Compliant with the CNL editor language
Description	The controlled natural language output of NLCS will be compliant with the language in input to the CNL Editor (meaning, must be the same)
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	NLCS.05
Short title	XML compliant

Description	The controlled natural language output of NLCS will be compliant with the XML based format supported by the CNL Editor.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

4.1.2.2 CNL Editor (HPE)

Requirement id	CNLE.01
Short title	CNL Editor GUI
Description	The controlled natural language Editor will have an interface accessible by web browser.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	CNLE.02
Short title	CNL Editor policies authoring
Description	The CNL Editor will allow creating statements for security controls.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	CNLE.03
Short title	CNL Editor input format
Description	The CNL Editor will accept as input NLCST format (XML based).
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	CNLE.04
Short title	CNL Editor policies changing
Description	The CNL Editor will allow changing input (policies) from NLCST.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	CNLE.05
Short title	CNL Editor vocabulary
Description	The CNL Editor will use an ontology-based vocabulary to model security controls. Ontology will be the same used by NLCST and based on W3C Web Ontology Language (OWL) standard format.
Status	Proposed

Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	CNLE.06
Short title	CNL Editor output format
Description	The CNL Editor will generate security controls with a XML format suitable for DSL mapper.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

4.1.2.3 DSL Mapper (CNR)

Requirement id	DSL.M.01
Short title	Translation to selected DSLs
Description	The controlled natural language output of NLCS and further edited— when needed— with the CNL editor, will be semi-automatically mapped (meaning, with little human intervention) to the enforceable languages (aka, Domain Specific Languages, DSLs) inputs to tools such as Cluditor, or whatever will be the chosen DSL in MEDINA.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

Requirement id	DSL.M.02
Short title	Mapping elements
Description	The mapping process will take into account relevant elements of the target certification framework, including (some) technical and organizational measures, quantitative/qualitative security metrics, complex compliance conditions, and cloud supply chain elements. The mapping process will prioritize the translation of those requirements in CNL that can automatically be enforced by WP4 and that are considered highly relevant by the EU authorities at stage.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR3
Reference	DoA, KR3 description

4.1.3 Risk based selection of controls Framework

Requirement id	RBSCF.01
Short title	Risk assessment tool
Description	The tool shall be based on a risk-assessment methodology and in order to help CSP, as well as an auditor, to identify the key assets, threats and existing weaknesses of the cloud system.
Status	Proposed

Requirement id	RBSCF.01
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR2
Reference	DoA. Page 8

Requirement id	RBSCF.02
Short title	Risk assessment tool and TOMs
Description	Identification of key assets, threats and existing weaknesses should support stakeholders in reflecting their chosen TOMs in accordance to their risk strategy, along with risk treatment options.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR2
Reference	DoA. Page 8

Requirement id	RBSCF.03
Short title	Implementation selection functionality
Description	MEDINA proposes a tool-supported methodology for the selection of controls and associated TOMs, which address the concrete needs of a CSP taking into consideration both its risk appetite and requested certification's assurance level ⁴ .
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR2
Reference	DoA. Page 8

Requirement id	RBSCF.04
Short title	Interface to the auditor
Description	Auditor follows a risk-based approach which provides flexibility to the certification process: since an ever-changing threat landscape often requires timely reaction from the security team provoking changes in the security configurations. These could be efficient from the risk treatment point of view, but will affect the previously obtained certificate, in the worst case, invalidating it.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR6
Reference	DoA. Page 9

4.1.4 Evidence gathering tools

4.1.4.1 Evidence Orchestrator

Requirement id	ECO.01
Short title	Provision of Interfaces
Description	The evidence orchestrator must provide standard interfaces for the evidence collection and assessment tools (T3.2-T3.4) to securely store their results.

Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	ECO.02
Short title	Conformity to selected assurance level
Description	The evidence orchestrator must ensure that the evidence collection (T3.2-T3.4) is performed according to the selected assurance level, i.e. it must trigger the evidence collection of the respective tools.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	ECO.03
Short title	Secure Transmission to evidence storage
Description	The evidence orchestrator must securely transmit evidences to the evidence storage.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

4.1.4.2 Evidence Trustworthiness management

Requirement id	ETM.01
Short title	Trustworthiness of evidences
Description	The evidence orchestrator must integrate reasonable safeguards for guaranteeing the trustworthiness of collected evidences.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	ETM.02
Short title	Transmission of evidence checksums
Description	The evidence orchestrator should integrate a Ledger client that stores checksums of evidences in a DLT.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	ETM.03
Short title	Trustworthiness guaranteeing capabilities

Requirement id	ETM.03
Description	Enable trustworthiness guaranteeing capabilities by extracting checksums from DLT and comparing with current checksums to detect modifications.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	ETM.04
Short title	Tamper-Resistance
Description	The developed tool must provide a tamper-proof way of storing evidence in the considered attacker model.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	ETM.05
Short title	Tamper-Resistance
Description	The DAT must provide a tamper-proof way of storing audit information in the considered attacker model.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

Requirement id	ETM.06
Short title	Compliance with existing standards
Description	The design and implementation of the DAT should comply with the requirements of existing standards regarding the certification chain (ISO-based approach, ISAE3402 and evidence-based).
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

4.1.4.3 *Technical evidences gathering tools: Clouditor, Codyze/CPG, Automated vulnerability monitoring / detection*

4.1.4.3.1 Common requirements to all the tools

Requirement id	TEGT.C.01
Short title	Continuous collection
Description	The developed tools must be able to collect evidences continuously, i.e. in (high)-frequency intervals.
Status	Proposed

Requirement id	TEGT.C.01
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	TEGT.C.02
Short title	Provision to defined interfaces
Description	The developed tools must provide collected evidences to a security assessment tool via its offered APIs.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

4.1.4.3.2 Specific tool requirements

Gathering evidence from cloud interfaces

Requirement id	TEGT.S.01
Short title	Collect evidences from cloud interfaces
Description	The developed tool must be able to collect evidences of cloud workloads, e.g. virtual machines, containers, and serverless functions.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Gathering evidence from application source code

Requirement id	TEGT.S.0.2
Short title	Collect evidences from source code via CPG
Description	The developed tool must be able to parse the source code of cloud applications written in different programming languages and transform into the agnostic representation of the CPG, and derive evidences from its analysis.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	TEGT.S.03
Short title	Implement information and data flow analysis
Description	The developed tool must be able to perform information and data flow analysis on a cloud application.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	TEGT.S.04
Short title	Support expression of security requirements
Description	The developed tool must be able to support the expression of security requirements to be checked on application code. Requirements come for example from WP2.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR1, KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	TEGT.S.05
Short title	Verify security requirements
Description	The developed tool must be able to verify security requirements and raise warnings/errors with respect to secure coding practices and secure information and data flows.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	TEGT.S.06
Short title	Retrieve source code of cloud applications
Description	The developed tool should be able to retrieve (semi-)automatically the source code of cloud applications requiring analysis.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	TEGT.S.07
Short title	Support for common programming languages, libraries, cloud services
Description	The developed tool should support common programming languages, libraries and cloud services. Support for all programming languages, libraries and cloud services is infeasible.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Gathering evidence from computing resources (VMs, containers, software)

Requirement id	TEGT.S.08
Short title	Provision of malware, intrusion, and vulnerability detection tools
Description	Tools for malware detection, intrusion detection, and vulnerability scanning must be provided to assist CSPs with satisfying related requirements of security standards or to verify the compliance with such requirements.
Status	Proposed

Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

4.1.4.4 Organizational evidences gathering and management

Requirement id	OEGM.01
Short title	Continuous collection of organizational evidences
Description	The developed tool using NLP must be able to collect organizational evidences continuously, i.e. in periodic intervals.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	OEGM.02
Short title	Provision to defined interfaces
Description	The developed tool using NLP must provide collected evidences to the respective security assessment tool via its offered APIs.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	OEGM.03
Short title	Usability for auditors
Description	The evidence management component should provide easy-to-use functionalities for auditors to search through relevant evidences, e.g. to identify the evidence that has triggered a change in the certificate state.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

Requirement id	OEGM.04
Short title	Minimum evidence storage
Description	The evidence management component must be able to store and provide evidence at least back to the last assessment.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR4
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 18-19

4.1.5 Evidences Assessment tool

Requirement id	EAT.01
Short title	Evidence assessment target

Requirement id	EAT.01
Description	The target values for the evidence assessment must be retrieved from a central repository of target values (WP2).
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

Requirement id	EAT.02
Short title	Continuous evidence assessment
Description	All evidence collection tools must forward evidences and measurement results (according to the data format defined in MEDINA) to the respective assessment components.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

Requirement id	EAT.03
Short title	Evidence assessment results
Description	The assessment results of evidence assessments must be submitted to the evidence orchestrator via the API it provides.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

4.1.6 Continuous certification evaluation

4.1.6.1 Continuous Cloud Security Certification evaluation

Requirement id	CCCE.01
Short title	Continuous Evaluation of Assessment Results
Description	The evaluation component must be able to continuously evaluate incoming assessment results and integrate them into the overall certification evaluation.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

Requirement id	CCCE.02
Short title	Evaluate the fulfilment degree per TOM
Description	The evaluation component must be able to evaluate continuously generated assessment results according to previously defined TOMs to calculate the degree of fulfilment per individual audited resource and for the TOM in general.
Status	Proposed

Requirement id	CCCE.02
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	CCCE.03
Short title	Configuration of needed metrics for requirements
Description	The evaluation component must be able to receive a selection of metrics needed to be satisfied for a particular requirement (as selected by the CSP) and consider it in the evaluation of requirements' fulfillment values.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	CCCE.04
Short title	Evaluate the fulfilment degree per control, control group, and entire certification
Description	The evaluation component must be able to aggregate the TOMs' fulfilment degrees to calculate the degree of fulfilment for controls, control groups, and the entire certification scheme.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	CCCE.05
Short title	Evaluate the temporal fulfilment degree per TOM
Description	The evaluation component should be able to evaluate continuously generated assessment results according to previously defined TOMs to calculate a degree of fulfilment over time.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	CCCE.06
Short title	Evaluate the time-to-fix indicator per TOM
Description	The evaluation component should be able to evaluate continuously generated assessment results to calculate a time-to-fix indicator.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	CCCE.07
Short title	APIs of the Continuous Certification Evaluation Component
Description	The evaluation component must provide APIs to the relevant components (evidences assessment tools) to receive assessment results, as well as to the digital audit trail and the certificate lifecycle management component to exchange relevant data.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

4.1.6.1 Automated certificate life-cycle management

Requirement id	ACLM.01
Short title	Cloud security certification issuance
Description	Based on the quality evaluation results, the system will push appropriate entities (CAB) to issue and sign security certifications for the cloud providers.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	ACLM.02
Short title	Automatic cloud security certification update
Description	Based on the quality evaluation results, the system will push appropriate entities (CAB) to update the security certifications for the cloud providers.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	ACLM.03
Short title	Cloud security certification revocation
Description	Based on quality evaluation results, the system will push appropriate entities (CAB) to revoke the security certifications for the cloud providers.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR5
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	ACLM.04
Short title	Continuous update of the certificate state
Description	The certificate lifecycle management component must continuously, i.e. in high-frequency intervals, convert the evaluation results from the CCE to the corresponding certificate state.
Status	Proposed

Requirement id	ACLM.04
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR6
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	ACLM.06
Short title	Compliance with EUCS assurance levels and certificate states
Description	The certificate lifecycle management component must map the certificate states and assurance levels defined in the EUCS scheme.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR6
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 page 22

Requirement id	ACLM.07
Short title	Interface for a public registry
Description	The lifecycle management component must provide an interface for publishing the certificate status in a public registry by the corresponding entities (CAB).
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR6
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

Requirement id	ACLM.08
Short title	Secure lifecycle management
Description	The lifecycle management component can be implemented in a smart contract to ensure a tamper-proof execution.
Status	To be evaluated
Priority	Can
Related KR	KR6
Reference	DoA part A Annex 1 pages 22

4.1.7 Risk-Based continuous assessment

Requirement id	RBCA.01
Short title	Dynamic risk assessment
Description	Timely adjust the CSP's risk profile and re-evaluate efficiency of security configuration
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR6
Reference	DoA. Page 9

Requirement id	RBCA.02
Short title	Interface to the continuous evidence management tools

Requirement id	RBCA.02
Description	Requires consuming the current status of the system configuration to re-adjust risk profile.
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	KR6
Reference	DoA. Page 9

4.2 Non-functional requirements

4.2.1 NF Requirements for development CI/CD tools

The NFRs are about the features the CI/CD tools should/must have in order to effectively meet the needs of the CI/CD strategy for the MEDINA project.

These requirements have been discussed with the partners and found agreement by all. Therefore, we intend to follow this methodology based on this NFRs to make decision for the CI/CD tools/products.

The assessment resulted in the requirements listed in the following tables.

Requirement id	CICD.01
Short title	Code repository
Description	The development environment has a Revision Control System for storing the source code of the project's components
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.02
Short title	Automate software build
Description	Speed up the build process by automating the steps necessary to produce executable and deployable software artefacts
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.03
Short title	Automate test suite
Description	Make the build process self-testing in order to spot early software defects, both at component/unit and at integration level
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.04
Short title	Software bugs tracking

Requirement id	CICD.04
Description	Facilitate the collection and monitoring of software issues in order to fix them with discipline
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.05
Short title	Deploy automation
Description	Automate the process of delivering the software in installable form in a bug-per-bug reproducible way
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.06
Short title	Free tools
Description	Selected tool are free or open source software, in order to allow the easy setup of the self-hosted development environments
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.07
Short title	Commercially friendliness tools
Description	The license is commercially friendly (i.e. Apache) and not copy-left, such in a way it does not impact on the developed software artefacts commercialization
Status	Proposed
Priority	Should
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.08
Short title	Java support
Description	Support Java programming language for MEDINA Framework
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.09
Short title	Python support

Description	Support Python programming language for MEDINA Framework
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.10
Short title	C language support
Description	Support C/C++ programming language for MEDINA Framework
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.11
Short title	GO Lang support
Description	Support GO programming language for MEDINA Framework
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

Requirement id	CICD.12
Short title	Javascript support
Description	Support Javascript/Typescript programming language for MEDINA Framework
Status	Proposed
Priority	Must
Related KR	Supporting Integration of KR1-KR5
Reference	DoA

4.2.2 MEDINA Deployment Models

This section briefly classifies MEDINA tool attending to the technological framework required for its execution and deployment. The section presents an initial classification of the KRs based on the envisioned deployment models at this initial stage of the project. This analysis will be extended and detailed in further versions of this deliverable from the technical perspective and in deliverable *D7.6 - Exploitation and sustainability Report* from the business model impact perspective.

The selection of the deployment model will be also influenced by the requirements of the certification stakeholders (i.e. auditors, CABs and NCCAs) who will only trust on the results gathered by the MEDINA tools because (i) they have participated in the implementation of the tools and (ii) the tools themselves are certified under the European Certification Framework, therefore a Continuous audit tools certification scheme is also needed.

4.2.2.1 Web tools (SaaS)

Are the tools accessible through any compatible browser?: In MEDINA some of the tools will be offered as service, which are invoked for performing different functionalities. Internally these

tools can be deployed following the multi-cloud approach. It is envisioned that the following MEDINA Key results, tools and components will be offered as Web Tools (SaaS):

- Repository of metrics and measures (KR1),
- Risk based selection of controls (KR2),
- Certification language (KR3),
- Cloud certificate Evaluator (KR5),
- Auditor Tool (KR6),
- The MEDINA framework.

4.2.2.2 Containerized tools

Containers are lightweight software components that bundle the application, its dependencies, and its configuration in a single image, running in isolated user environments on a traditional operating system on a traditional server or in a virtualized environment [6]. Containerization of an application has several advantages as, for example:

- Portability between different platforms and clouds: write once, run anywhere. An application in a container behaves the same regardless the environment where it is deployed, avoiding issues with operating system versions
- Efficiency through using far fewer resources than VMs and delivering higher utilization of compute resources.
- Improved security by isolating applications from the host system and from each other.
- Faster app start-up and easier and cost-effective scaling.
- Flexibility to work on virtualized infrastructures or on bare metal servers.
- Easier management since install, upgrade, and rollback processes can be built into the Kubernetes platform.
- It allows developers to integrate with their existing DevOps environment (more on this aspect can be read in chapter 6. MEDINA DevOps infrastructure and CI/CD and verification strategy).

This case is similar to the previous one, but in this case the web application can be installed locally. The difference between this case and the previous one depends on the exploitation model to be decided for each Key Result, tool or component and also the needs from the users with respect to the usage of the component / tool (i.e. evidences storage shall be internal (local) to the CSP)). The following tools fit into this category:

- Repository of metrics and measures (KR1),
- Risk based selection of controls (KR2),
- Certification language (KR3),
- Cloud certificate Evaluator (KR5),
- Auditor Tool (KR6),
- The MEDINA framework,
- Continuous evidence management tool (KR4).

4.2.2.3 Others

Other components may be delivered as software libraries or software clients to be included/imported in other software tools from the CSPs/Auditors. This might be the case for the orchestrator component inside the Continuous evidence management tool (KR4).

4.3 MEDINA framework requirements analysis

4.3.1 Functional requirements and KRs alignment

The functional requirements are defined in section 4.1. Following, the list of Key Results of the MEDINA project, defined first in the DoA, is presented:

- KR1: Repository of metrics and measures
- KR2: Risk based selection of controls
- KR3: Certification language
- KR4: Continuous evidence management tool
- KR5: Cloud certificate Evaluator
- KR6: Auditor Tool
- KR7: MEDINA Use Cases

As a result, it can be affirmed that all the elicited Functional Requirements are related to one/or more specific KR.

Table 2. Functional requirements and KRs alignment matrix

	Req. ID	KR1	KR2	KR3	KR4	KR5	KR6
1	RCME.01	X					
2	RCME.02	X					
3	RCME.03	X					
4	RCME.04	X					
5	RCME.05	X					
6	RCME.06	X					
7	NLCS.01			X			
8	NLCS.02			X			
9	NLCS.03			X			
10	NLCS.04			X			
11	NLCS.05			X			
12	CNLE.01			X			
13	CNLE.02			X			
14	CNLE.03			X			
15	CNLE.04			X			
16	CNLE.05			X			
17	CNLE.06			X			
18	DSL.M.01			X			
19	DSL.M.02			X			
20	RBSCF.01		X				
21	RBSCF.02		X				
22	RBSCF.03		X				
23	RBSCF.04		X				X
24	ECO.01				X		
25	ECO.02				X		
26	ECO.03				X		
27	ETM.01				X		
28	ETM.02				X		
29	ETM.03				X		
30	ETM.04				X		
31	ETM.05				X	X	

	Req. ID	KR1	KR2	KR3	KR4	KR5	KR6
32	ETM.06				X	X	
33	TEGT.C.01				X		
34	TEGT.C.02				X		
35	TEGT.S.01				X		
36	TEGT.S.02				X		
37	TEGT.S.03				X		
38	TEGT.S.04				X		
39	TEGT.S.05				X		
40	TEGT.S.06				X		
41	TEGT.S.07				X		
42	TEGT.S.08				X		
43	OEGM.01				X		
44	OEGM.02				X		
45	OEGM.03				X		
46	OEGM.04				X		
47	EAT.01				X		
48	EAT.02				X		
49	EAT.03				X		
50	CCCE.01					X	
51	CCCE.02					X	
52	CCCE.03					X	
53	CCCE.04					X	
54	CCCE.05					X	
55	CCCE.06					X	
56	CCCE.07					X	
57	ACLM.01					X	
58	ACLM.01					X	
59	ACLM.02					X	
60	ACLM.03					X	
61	ACLM.04					X	
62	ACLM.06					X	
63	ACLM.08					X	
64	RBCA.01						X
65	RBCA.02						X

4.3.2 Use cases requirements and modules alignment

This section shows the alignment between the Use Cases requirements and the KRs and modules.

This alignment tries to show that each of the requirements defined by the Use Cases owners has one or more corresponding module/submodules that implements it. This way, a user can check the responsible module for implementing a requirement and track the coverage of the requirements along the time. A requirement with no associated KR or module means that either it is out of scope of MEDINA framework or that the framework has to extend its functionalities.

At the same time, this table will serve for the components designers to identify potential missing functionalities from the UCs needs perspective, and to align both the bottom up perspective and the top down approach followed in MEDINA for the elicitation of the requirements.

Table 3. Use Case requirements and KR alignment matrix

Req. ID	Short Title	KR1	KR2	KR3	KR4	KR5	KR6
COMMON							
UC00.01	MEDINA Audit API	X		X	X	X	X
UC00.02	Repository of Security Controls	X	X				
UC00.04	Secure Evidence Storage				X		
UC00.05	Evidence Mapping				X		
UC00.06	Security Controls Translator			X			
UC00.07	Define Measurement Targets			X		X	X
UC00.08	Add Traditional Audit results to MEDINA results					X	X
UC00.09	Request for Change on Assessment Rules	X	X	X		X	
UC00.11	Assessment Results return value	X	X	X		X	
UC00.13	Auditor access to Assessment Results				X	X	X
UC00.14	Compliance Status notification					X	X
UC00.16	MEDINA Measurement Target run-time change				X	X	X
UC00.17	MEDINA complies to EUCS	X					
UC00.18	MEDINA tool modularity			X	X	X	X
UC00.19	Mapping of Frameworks	X	X				
UC00.20	Scalable Framework		X		X	X	X
UC00.21	Interoperability API				X	X	
UC00.22	Data collection extent				X		
UC00.23	Retention of evidences				X		
UC00.24	Compliance Certification Status						X
UC00.25	Efficiency Improvements (Automation)						X
UC00.26	Efficiency Improvements						X
UC00.27	Monitoring of Organizational Measures				X		X
UC00.28	Report Generation				X		X
UC00.29	Unified Graphical User Interface						X
UC00.30	Internal Regulation Checks Support	X	X	X			
UC00.31	Trustworthiness of Evidences				X	X	X
UC00.32	Attribution of Security Controls		X	X			
USE CASE 01							
UC01.1	Compliance Status Aggregation on Corporate Level					X	X
UC01.2	Compliance Dashboard on Corporate Level					X	X
UC01.3	Misconfiguration Monitoring on Corporate Level					X	X
UC01.4	Non-compliance Monitoring on Corporate Level					X	X
UC01.5	Aggregate Attribution of Non-Compliances					X	X
UC01.6	Graphical User Interface			X	X	X	X
UC01.7	Misconfiguration Tracking				X	X	X
UC01.9	Compliance Certification Status on Corporate Level					X	X
UC01.10	Compliance Status Aggregation on Domain Level					X	X
UC01.11	Compliance Status Aggregation on Domain Level					X	X
UC01.12	Compliance Status Aggregation on Domain Level					X	X
UC01.14	Compliance Certification Status on Domain Level					X	X
UC01.15	Misconfiguration Monitoring on Product Level				X	X	X
UC01.16	Non-compliance Monitoring on Product Level				X	X	X
UC01.17	Feedback on Remediation Actions				X	X	X
UC01.18	Provision of Remediation Guidance	X					X
UC01.19	Configuration		X		X		
UC01.20	Compliance Certification Status on Product Level				X	X	X
UC01.21	Compliance and Certification Status in Product Composition				X	X	X
UC01.22	Integration with Asset Management				X	X	
UC01.23	Framework Tools Setup and Configuration Automation				X	X	
UC01.24	User Interface Single Pane of Glass		X		X	X	X

UC01.25	User Interface Time and Product Scope Adjustability				X	X	X
UC01.26	Selectable Certification Schemes and Security Frameworks		X	X			
UC01.27	Selectable Controls in Compliance Dashboard				X	X	
UC01.28	Identification of Compliance Issues in Composed Products / Services				X	X	X
UC01.29	Integration with Cloud-native Security Posture Management				X		
UC01.30	Interfaces for the Provision of Organizational Evidences				X		
UC01.31	Product-specific Customization of Certification Scheme	X	X				
USE CASE 02							
UC02.01	Dashboard for the Compliance Manager	X	X				
UC02.02	Delegation of compliance tasks from Compliance Manager to Internal Control Owner		X				
UC02.03	Set up of Internal Control by Compliance Manager			X		X	
UC02.04	Mapping of Internal Controls to Security Controls by Compliance Manager or ICO	X	X	X			
UC02.05	Application to the same Security Control Framework to different Subsidiaries or Projects of the Corporation		X		X	X	X
UC02.06	Tracking of Internal Controls by Compliance Manager						X
UC02.07	Comprisal of Implementation Report by Compliance Manager for Auditor						X
UC02.08	Comprisal of Report by Compliance Manager						X
UC02.09	Elimination of risk for non-compliance						X
UC02.10	Sleek UI						
UC02.12	Accept or decline ownership of Security Control		X				
UC02.13	Change status of Internal Control		X	X	X		X

A more detailed correspondence among Use cases requirements and their implementation can be seen in the Table 4, where we reflect the component that implements each requirement. A second column has been added to include a second component because some requirements, in the actual definition, includes several aspects so that their implementation requires more than a single component. Each requirement coming from the Use Cases has to be implemented by (at least) one component. Otherwise, this would mean that no component is implementing such requirement.

Table 4. Use Case requirements and Components alignment matrix

Req. ID	Component	2nd Component
COMMON		
UC00.01	Automated certificate life-cycle management	Evidence collection orchestration
UC00.02	Repository of controls, metrics...	
UC00.04	Evidence collection orchestration	Evidence trustworthiness management
UC00.05	Evidence trustworthiness management	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool
UC00.06	NLCS translator	CNL Editor
UC00.07	CNL Editor	
UC00.08	Evidence collection orchestration	
UC00.09	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	
UC00.11	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	
UC00.13	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	
UC00.14	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	Automated certificate l-c management
UC00.16	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	
UC00.17	Automated certificate life-cycle management	Repository of controls, metrics...
UC00.18	Evidence collection orchestration	
UC00.19	Repository of controls, metrics...	DSL Mapper
UC00.20	Automated certificate life-cycle management	

Req. ID	Component	2nd Component
UC00.21	Automated certificate life-cycle management	Audit UI
UC00.22	Evidence collection orchestration	
UC00.23	Evidence collection orchestration	
UC00.24	Automated certificate life-cycle management	
UC00.25	Evidence collection orchestration	Audit UI
UC00.26	Continuous Cloud Certificate Evaluation	Audit UI
UC00.27	Organizational evidences gathering and mgmt.	Audit UI
UC00.28	Automated certificate life-cycle management	Continuous Cloud Certificate Evaluation
UC00.29	Automated certificate life-cycle management	
UC00.30	Audit UI	
UC00.31	Evidence trustworthiness management	
UC00.32	Continuous Cloud Certificate Evaluation	
USE CASE 01		
UC01.1	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.2	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.3	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.4	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.5	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.6	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.7	Company Compliance Dashboard	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool
UC01.9	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.10	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.11	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.12	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.14	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.15	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.16	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.17	Company Compliance Dashboard	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool
UC01.18	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.19	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	
UC01.20	Repository of controls, metrics...	Company Compliance Dashboard
UC01.21	Evidence collection orchestration	
UC01.22	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.23	Evidence collection orchestration	
UC01.24	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	
UC01.25	Technical Evidences gathering tool	
UC01.26	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.27	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.28	Risk based selection of controls Framework	Company Compliance Dashboard
UC01.29	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.30	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC01.31	Evidence collection orchestration	
USE CASE 02		
UC02.01	Company Compliance Dashboard	Repository of controls, metrics...
UC02.02	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC02.03	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC02.04	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC02.05	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC02.06	Company Compliance Dashboard	Automated certificate l-c management
UC02.07	Company Compliance Dashboard	Automated certificate l-c management
UC02.08	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC02.09	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC02.10	Company Compliance Dashboard	
UC02.12	Company Compliance Dashboard	

Req. ID	Component	2nd Component
UC02.13	Company Compliance Dashboard	

Next table, Table 5, that can be considered a different view of the information already contained in the previous table, lists all the components defined in MEDINA and reflects which UC requirement is implemented by each component.

Table 5. Components and Use Case requirements alignment matrix

#	Components	Use Cases // For secondary component
1	Repository of controls, metrics, measures & evidences	UC00: 02, 19 // UC00.17 UC01: 20 UC02: // UC00.01
2	NLCS translator	UC00: 06
3	CNL Editor	UC00: 07 // UC00.06
4	DSL Mapper	UC00: // UC00.19
5	Risk based selection of controls Framework	UC01: 28
6	Evidence collection orchestration	UC00: 04, 08, 18, 22, 23, 25 UC01: 21, 23, 31
7	Evidence trustworthiness management	UC00: 05, 31 // UC00.04
8	Technical Evidences gathering tool	UC01: 25
9	Organizational evidences gathering and management	UC00: 27
10	Continuous Evidence Assessment Tool	UC00: 09, 11, 13, 14, 16 // UC00.05 UC01: 19, 24 // UC01.07, 17
11	Continuous Cloud Certificate Evaluation	UC00: 26, 32 // UC00.28
12	Automated certificate life-cycle management	UC00: 01, 17,20,21,24,28,29 // UC00.14 UC02: 06, 07
13	Risk based continuous assessment	-
14	Audit UI	UC00: 30 // UC00.21, 25, 26, 27
15	Company Compliance Dashboard	UC01: 01,02,03,04,05,06,07,09,10,11,12, 14,15,16,17,18,22,26,27,29,30 // 20, 28 UC02:01,02,03,04,05,06,07,08,09,10,12, 13

4.3.3 Requirements prioritization

This section provides an overview of the status of the functional requirements elicited during the first year of the project. For each of these requirements, we indicate the expected implementation deadline, according to the prioritization carried out.

It has to be noted that this is the state of things at the moment of writing (month 12). This information will be updated as the project progresses and is foreseen that more and more requirements will be implemented. We distinguish among Partially covered or Fully covered.

Table 6. Requirements prioritization matrix

Main component	Req. ID	Priority	Due date		
			M15	M27	M33
KR1 Repository of controls	RCME.01	MUST	Fully	Fully	Fully
	RCME.02	MUST	Fully	Fully	Fully
	RCME.03	MUST	Fully	Fully	Fully
	RCME.04	MUST	-	Fully	Fully

Main component	Req. ID	Priority	Due date		
			M15	M27	M33
	RCME.05	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	RCME.06	MUST	-	Partially	Partially
KR3 Certification Language	NLCS.01	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	NLCS.02	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	NLCS.03	MUST	Partially	Partially	Partially
	NLCS.04	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	NLCS.05	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	CNLE.01	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	CNLE.02	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	CNLE.03	Should	-	Partially	Fully
	CNLE.04	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	CNLE.05	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	CNLE.06	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	DSL.M.01	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	DSL.M.02	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	KR2 Risk based selection of controls	RBSCF.01	MUST	-	Partially
RBSCF.02		MUST	-	Partially	Fully
RBSCF.03		MUST	-	Partially	Fully
RBSCF.04		MUST	-	Partially	Fully
KR4 Continuous evidence management tools	ECO.01	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	ECO.02	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	ECO.03	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	ETM.01	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	ETM.02	Should	Partially	Partially	Fully
	ETM.03	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	ETM.04	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	ETM.05	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	ETM.06	Should	Partially	Partially	Fully
	TEGT.C.01	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	TEGT.C.02	MUST	Fully	Fully	Fully
	TEGT.S.01	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	TEGT.S.02	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	TEGT.S.03	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	TEGT.S.04	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	TEGT.S.05	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	TEGT.S.06	Should	-	Partially	Fully
	TEGT.S.07	Should	Partially	Partially	Fully
	TEGT.S.08	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	OEGM.01	MUST	-	Partially	Partially
OEGM.02	MUST	-	Partially	Partially	
OEGM.03	Should	-	Partially	Partially	
OEGM.04	MUST	-	Partially	Fully	
KR5 Continuous certification evaluation	EAT.01	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	EAT.02	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	EAT.03	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	CCCE.01	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	CCCE.02	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	CCCE.03	MUST	-Partially	Partially	Fully

Main component	Req. ID	Priority	Due date		
			M15	M27	M33
	CCCE.04	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	CCCE.05	Should	Partially	Partially	Fully
	CCCE.06	Should	-	Partially	Fully
	CCCE.07	MUST	Partially	Partially	Fully
	ACLM.01	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	ACLM.01	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	ACLM.02	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	ACLM.03	MUST	Partially	Fully	Fully
	ACLM.04	MUST	Fully	Fully	Fully
	ACLM.06	MUST	Fully	Fully	Fully
KR6 Risk-Based continuous assessment	ACLM.08	Can	-	tbd*	tbd*
	RBCA.01	MUST	-	Partially	Fully
	RBCA.02	MUST	-	Partially	Fully

(*) To be defined: some requirements are still under discussion

From the table we can extract some statistical data about the implementation plans in MEDINA. For example:

- At M15 (V1) 40% of the requirements are to be implemented, at least partially.
- At M27 (V2) 75% of the requirements are foreseen to be partially implemented.
- At M33 (V3) 91% of the requirements is expected to be fully implemented, and 99% at least partially implemented.

5 MEDINA Framework architecture

This section presents the first version of the MEDINA architecture. To create this version of the architecture, the process depicted in the next figure was performed, which comprises the following activities:

- Analysis of the MEDINA workflow and alternatives: An overview of this workflow is explained in section 5.1.
- In parallel to the workflow definition the overall architecture with all the components was designed. This is explained in section 5.1.
- Once the overall architecture was discussed the structural and behavioural description of the components conforming the MEDINA framework has been detailed (section 5.3).
- As part of the architecture definition, the deployment options of the components and the Framework itself have been discussed and analysed.

Figure 5. Process followed in MEDINA to develop the MEDINA architecture

5.1 Overview of the MEDINA framework

The architectural framework proposed by MEDINA can be abstracted in the seven building blocks shown in Figure 6, which are explained in the rest of this subsection. Each building block corresponds to a well differentiated functionality of the proposed architecture, which will be further developed in upcoming WP5 deliverables and instantiated by the use cases in WP6.

Figure 6. Building blocks view of the MEDINA framework.

The first building block relates to the set of catalogues being required by the different roles and personas interacting with MEDINA (please refer to Deliverable 6.1 [2]), which comprise the different elements of a control's framework like EUCS. We refer to catalogues of controls, metrics, TOMs' reference implementations, and target values being suggested to CSPs. This building block also leverages reporting functionalities targeting specific roles e.g. CABs and compliance managers.

Then we have a second block which implements the NLP techniques proposed by MEDINA (see WP2) to guarantee that new requirements from EUCS, or other catalogues, are related to the metrics in the catalogue referenced in the previous paragraph. This building block leverages a novel ontology to guarantee that requirements written in natural language are automatically associated to CSP-specific resources. Our goal is to automatize the current (manual) process performed by compliance managers and auditors to interpret, map, implement, and assess requirements in their own organizations.

The risk assessment functionalities provided by MEDINA, both static and dynamic, can be seen in the third building block of the architecture shown in Figure 6. Those functionalities take as input the MEDINA catalogue of controls & security schemes and, based on the CSP's risk appetite and assessment results, can control the certification lifecycle (see building block 4).

A core building block in our framework comprises the components that manage the lifecycle of the certification, which depends on the rules established by the corresponding scheme (EUCS in the case of MEDINA). This is the fourth building block in our framework where National Certification Bodies (NCB), or even pan-European entities like ENISA, can benefit from by becoming public registers of issued certificates. Our goal is to provide fully automated lifecycle management, which depends on dynamic risk assessment techniques and the automation of the security assessment processes implemented by MEDINA.

A state of practice challenge for providing automation of auditing/certification relates to the processing of organizational measures, where related documentation of the CSP (e.g. security concepts, operation manuals) is assessed for conformance with the certification scheme's requirements. Building block five in MEDINA's framework implements both a repository for those organizational evidences, and the NLP-based techniques for their processing.

Complementary to this functionality in MEDINA, is building block seven, which provides the assessment of technical measures by integrating a variety of tools (including native CSP functionalities). This building block seven targets the multi-layer assessment of the target-of-certification cloud service i.e. the related IaaS, PaaS and SaaS stack.

All gathered assessment results, either from organizational (block 5) or technical measures (block 7), are holistically stored and processed by the components shown in building block 6. Both an orchestrator (in charge of managing the collected evidences and assessment results), and a DLT-enabled evidence manager (to guarantee tamper proof storage of evidences) are core components of this building block.

Finally, building block 8 provides a MEDINA user interface to facilitate human interaction with the components in building block 7. Take for example a corporate compliance manager who visualizes the near real-time status of issued EUCS certificates, or an external CAB reviewing the evidence used for a certification process.

5.2 MEDINA data model

In this section the current version of the MEDINA data model is presented. This data model describes the different entities (and their attributes) that will be used and shared by the components in MEDINA. The entities have been categorized into different groups depending on the building block/WP they belong to:

- Blue entities: Repository of controls and metrics
- Grey entities: Risk Assessment and optimisation framework
- Orange entities: Repository of controls and metrics and MEDINA ontology
- Red entities: Evidence assessment

- Green entities: Evidence gathering and assessment
- Purple entities: Evidence and assessment result trustworthiness
- Dark orange entities: Cloud security certification

Figure 7. MEDINA framework data model.

This data model is an evolving resource that is updated periodically by the technical partners in charge of the implementation of the technical components.. The concepts are described in each of the description’s components in the technical WPs (WP2, WP3, WP4).

5.3 MEDINA components structural and behavioural description

This section presents the different components which are part of the MEDINA framework.

The first group of components (section 5.3.1) are described through component cards including their requirements, sequence diagrams, interfaces, etc. which provides the structural and behavioural description of the components. These components are the ones which are core to the MEDINA framework and will be implemented in the context of MEDINA action. In section 5.3.2, components relevant for MEDINA are described. These components are not treated in the same way in terms of components description, for different reasons, i.e. not regular “software” components, components that will not be developed in the context of MEDINA but they will be used or integrated on the solution, etc. At the time this report was written two components were included in section 5.3.2.

5.3.1 Component cards

5.3.1.1 Catalogue of controls and security schemes

Component Name	Catalogue of controls and security schemes
Main functionalities	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Endorsement of Security Control Frameworks and related attributes: Security requirements, categories, controls, reference TOMs, metrics, evidences and assurance levels. • Provision of guidance for the (self-)assessment of the requirements. • Filtering of the information based on some values for the attributes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Selection of requirements of a certain assurance level

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Selection of requirements from a certain framework ○ Selection of metrics related to reference TOM ○ Etc. ● Homogenization of the certification schemes: Provision of information about related requirements from different frameworks especially referenced to the EUCS. 									
Sub-components Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Security Control Frameworks (SFC) registry: The Security Control Frameworks registry will store the available list of Frameworks and the related info for a specific CSP. This component will also include corresponding databases. ● SFC back-end: The SFC backend is the core sub-component of the Catalogue. It will perform the actual discovery of the requirements, evidences, etc. from the Security Control Frameworks registry, considering the set of filters established by the user through the UI/ API. ● SFC frontend: This sub-component is the graphical user interface of the SFC. This SFC frontend will allow the user to indicate his requirements to filter and select a set of information related to the existing frameworks, i.e requirements of a certain assurance level , requirements from a certain framework, metrics related to reference TOM, references TOMs, guidance, etc. 									
Main logical Interfaces	<p>Include graphical interfaces if any.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="448 1025 1350 1328"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interface name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>SFC UI</td> <td>Graphical user interface of the SFC</td> <td>Angular and Bootstrap</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Discover requirements</td> <td>Select a set of requirements (and related attributes) for a given CS</td> <td>Rest API</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interface name	Description	Interface technology	SFC UI	Graphical user interface of the SFC	Angular and Bootstrap	Discover requirements	Select a set of requirements (and related attributes) for a given CS	Rest API
Interface name	Description	Interface technology								
SFC UI	Graphical user interface of the SFC	Angular and Bootstrap								
Discover requirements	Select a set of requirements (and related attributes) for a given CS	Rest API								
Requirements Mapping	<p>List of requirements covered by this component:</p> <p>RCME.01, RCME.02, RCME.03, RCME.04, RCME.05, RCME.06</p>									
Interaction with other components	<table border="1" data-bbox="448 1451 1350 1648"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interfacing Component</th> <th>Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>NLCS editor</td> <td>NLCS editor will request to the Catalogue the requirements and related information for a certain user</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	NLCS editor	NLCS editor will request to the Catalogue the requirements and related information for a certain user					
Interfacing Component	Interface Description									
NLCS editor	NLCS editor will request to the Catalogue the requirements and related information for a certain user									

Relevant sequence diagram/s	
Current TRL	Based on exiting tools (ACSmi-Tecnia)
Programming language	<p>jHipster framework based on microservices architecture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Java stack on the server side with Spring Boot • Frontend with Angular and Bootstrap
License	Apache license v2.0
WP and task	<p>WP2-T2.1, T2.2</p> <p>WP3-T3.1, T3.3</p>

5.3.1.2 NLCS translator

Component Name	CNL translator
Main functionalities	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translates the natural language text (English) of Security Requirements (TOMs) to the CNL obligations by recommending/predicting a set of metrics and integrating them into the CNL
Sub-components Description	<p>Recommender system:</p> <p>Maps/assigns a set of metrics to a requirement.</p>
Sub-components Description	<p>Obligation builder:</p> <p>Takes the predicted metric, the predefined target value, the operator and the definition of the resource (probably from ontology).</p> <p>Obl = op(M(R), TV) -> returns Boolean</p> <p>Obl = op(MV, TV) -> returns Boolean</p>

Sub-components Description	<p>Optional component: Database</p> <p>Stores the obligations and associated metadata like requirement-ID etc.</p> <p>We would prefer to include this in a sub-database in repository of controls.</p>						
Main logical Interfaces	<p>Include graphical interfaces if any.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 25%;">Interface name</th> <th style="width: 45%;">Description</th> <th style="width: 30%;">Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Database access</td> <td>An interface that provides access to stored TOMs and metrics</td> <td>REST</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Database access	An interface that provides access to stored TOMs and metrics	REST
Interface name	Description	Interface technology					
Database access	An interface that provides access to stored TOMs and metrics	REST					
Requirements Mapping	<p>List of requirements covered by this component</p> <p>NLCS.01-NLCS.05</p>						
Interaction with other components	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;">Interfacing Component</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Catalogue of metrics and controls component or the database</td> <td>Read metrics, requirements and store the CNL obligations linked to both</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Catalogue of metrics and controls component or the database	Read metrics, requirements and store the CNL obligations linked to both		
Interfacing Component	Interface Description						
Catalogue of metrics and controls component or the database	Read metrics, requirements and store the CNL obligations linked to both						
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram actor User as CNL translator user participant Translator as CNL translator participant API as Catalogue of controls API User->>Translator: dispatch activate Translator Translator->>API: get metrics and requirements activate API API-->>Translator: return metric and requiremnts deactivate API Translator->>API: store CNL obligations deactivate Translator </pre>						
Current TRL	to be developed from scratch						
Programming language	Python 3.x						
License	To be decided						
WP and task	WP2 Task 2.3						

5.3.1.3 CNL editor

Component Name	CNL Editor										
Main functionalities	The component provides the following functionalities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CNL Editor will allow work on CNL document, i.e. a requirement description (metadata) + a list of metrics in the form of a list of Obligations. • CNL Editor will allow to create a CNL document from scratch (to be verified). • CNL Editor will allow to add or delete metrics from an already filled CNL document. • CNL Editor will allow to update obligations parameters (range, target value) based on the Editor ontology. 										
Sub-components Description	CNL Editor UI: Web GUI Interface for users, with authentication and user profiling OWL vocabulary: stores Ontology used by Editor Editor API: to access CNL documents from external clients/components Back Store Interface: to access Internally CNL Store CNL Store: document-oriented storage										
Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any. <table border="1" data-bbox="443 1128 1348 1393"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interface name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>CNL Editor UI</td> <td>CNL Editor Web GUI</td> <td>HTTP (browser)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Editor API</td> <td>API to access CNL documents</td> <td>REST API</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Interface name	Description	Interface technology	CNL Editor UI	CNL Editor Web GUI	HTTP (browser)	Editor API	API to access CNL documents	REST API
Interface name	Description	Interface technology									
CNL Editor UI	CNL Editor Web GUI	HTTP (browser)									
Editor API	API to access CNL documents	REST API									
Requirements Mapping	List of requirements covered by this component CNLE.01, CNLE.02, CNLE.03, CNLE.04, CNLE.05, CNLE.06										
Interaction with other components	Interfacing Component	Interface Description									
	CNL Translator	CNL Editor reads CNL documents in XML format as prepared by CNL Translator									
	DSL Mapper	CNL Editor provides to DSL Mapper the finalised CNL documents to be mapped									
	Catalogue of metrics, controls and TOMs	CNL Editor reads pre-defined metrics to be included in CNL document									

Relevant sequence diagram/s	
Current TRL	Based on exiting tools/components (HPE)
Programming language	Java, Springboot,GWT
License	Apache 2.0
WP and task	WP2 T2.4

Component Name	CNL Editor Ontology						
Main functionalities	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ontology is needed for CNL Editor functioning: Obligation for metrics can be composed using Ontology Terms • Ontology allows to write or change Metrics associated to a Requirements respecting ontology rules and Vocabulary defined 						
Sub-components Description	OWL vocabulary: stores Ontology used by Editor						
Main logical Interfaces	<p>OWL vocabulary is a file in RDF/XML format that is used on reading internally from CNL Editor</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 33%;">Interface name</th> <th style="width: 33%;">Description</th> <th style="width: 33%;">Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Protégé⁵</td> <td>Protégé Desktop is a feature rich ontology editing environment</td> <td>Windows Desktop</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Protégé ⁵	Protégé Desktop is a feature rich ontology editing environment	Windows Desktop
Interface name	Description	Interface technology					
Protégé ⁵	Protégé Desktop is a feature rich ontology editing environment	Windows Desktop					

⁵ <https://protege.stanford.edu/>

		with full support for the OWL 2 Web Ontology Language and is W3C Standard Compliant					
Requirements Mapping	List of requirements covered by this component (refer to the requirements in D5.1) CNLE.02, CNLE.04, CNLE.05						
Interaction with other components	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interfacing Component</th> <th>Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>CNL Editor</td> <td>CNL Editor reads vocabulary (OWL file)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Interfacing Component	Interface Description	CNL Editor	CNL Editor reads vocabulary (OWL file)
Interfacing Component	Interface Description						
CNL Editor	CNL Editor reads vocabulary (OWL file)						
Relevant sequence diagram/s	see CNL Editor Sequence Diagram						
Current TRL	Based on exiting tools/components (HPE)						
Programming language	To be decided						
License	To be decided						
WP and task	WP2 T2.4						

5.3.1.4 DSL mapper

Component Name	DSL mapper								
Main functionalities	The component provides the following functionalities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of the CNL obligations + metadata output to a DSL (e.g. rego) 								
Sub-components Description	To be defined/ there are no sub-components								
Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any. <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interface name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Database access</td> <td>Read the CNL obligations + metadata from the database and write the DSL (rego code)</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Database access	Read the CNL obligations + metadata from the database and write the DSL (rego code)	
Interface name	Description	Interface technology							
Database access	Read the CNL obligations + metadata from the database and write the DSL (rego code)								

Requirements Mapping	List of requirements covered by this component DSL.M.01, DSL.M.02				
Interaction with other components	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interfacing Component</th> <th>Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Catalogue of metrics and controls component or the database or CNL translator</td> <td>Read all necessary metadata, metrics and CNL obligations and store rego assessment rules</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Catalogue of metrics and controls component or the database or CNL translator	Read all necessary metadata, metrics and CNL obligations and store rego assessment rules
Interfacing Component	Interface Description				
Catalogue of metrics and controls component or the database or CNL translator	Read all necessary metadata, metrics and CNL obligations and store rego assessment rules				
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant DSL_mapper as DSL mapper participant Catalogue_API as Catalogue of controls API DSL_mapper->>DSL_mapper: dispatch DSL_mapper->>Catalogue_API: read CNL obligations Catalogue_API-->>DSL_mapper: CNL obligations DSL_mapper-->>Catalogue_API: rego rules </pre>				
Current TRL	to be developed from scratch				
Programming language	Python				
License	To be decided				
WP and task	WP2 Task 2.5				

5.3.1.5 Risk assessment and optimisation framework

Component Name	Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework (aka Risk-based selection of controls Framework, SARTA)
Main functionalities	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Assessment – a questionnaire-based risk assessment facility to evaluate CSP-specific risk levels for predefined threats. • Cost-Effective TOMs optimisation – selection the most cost-effective requirements/TOMs (to optimise investment), in case Certification Framework allows this (in contrast to rigid Frameworks). • Risk-based analysis of deviations – risk-based evaluation of deviation from the framework to determine if the deviation is major or minor.

<p>Sub-components Description</p>	<p>Risk Assessment Engine – computes risk levels using the pre-established relations between asset types, threats and requirements. Requires the list of assets and implemented requirements as input.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk Assessment GUI – is the user-friendly front-end part of the Framework which guides a user (compliance manager) through the steps for identification of main input parameters and displays results of the analysis. • Risk Assessment API – is a set of APIs which collect the main input parameters and provide the results of the analysis in a machine-readable format. <p>In case all interactions with MEDINA are performed through Compliance Manager Dashboard only, only API is relevant.</p> <p>Risk optimiser Engine – selects the most cost-relevant TOMs to optimise the expected expenditure (risk + cost) given the budget or to ensure compliance with the selected Certification Framework.</p> <p>Risk-based decision support— compares two risk assessment results (basic and actual ones) and decides if the deviation is major or minor.</p> <p>Risk storage – the storage of the current risk practices settings.</p>												
<p>Main logical Interfaces</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interface name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Risk Assessment GUI</td> <td>Graphical user interface of risk assessment</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Risk Assessment APIs</td> <td>A set of machine-readable APIs for risk assessment</td> <td>Rest API</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Deviation reporting API</td> <td>The API used for analysis and reporting a detected deviation</td> <td>Rest API</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Risk Assessment GUI	Graphical user interface of risk assessment		Risk Assessment APIs	A set of machine-readable APIs for risk assessment	Rest API	Deviation reporting API	The API used for analysis and reporting a detected deviation	Rest API
Interface name	Description	Interface technology											
Risk Assessment GUI	Graphical user interface of risk assessment												
Risk Assessment APIs	A set of machine-readable APIs for risk assessment	Rest API											
Deviation reporting API	The API used for analysis and reporting a detected deviation	Rest API											
<p>Requirements Mapping</p>	<p>List of requirements covered by this component</p> <p>RBSCF.01, RBSCF.02, RBSCF.03, RBSCF.04, RBCA.01, RBCA.02</p>												
<p>Interaction with other components</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interfacing Component</th> <th>Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Compliance manager (Dashboard)</td> <td>Invokes Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework for selection of suggested requirements to implement, analysis of (goal) security configuration (e.g. for deviation from the target security configuration set by a certification framework), setting up resources and possible impact.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Compliance manager (Dashboard)	Invokes Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework for selection of suggested requirements to implement, analysis of (goal) security configuration (e.g. for deviation from the target security configuration set by a certification framework), setting up resources and possible impact.								
Interfacing Component	Interface Description												
Compliance manager (Dashboard)	Invokes Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework for selection of suggested requirements to implement, analysis of (goal) security configuration (e.g. for deviation from the target security configuration set by a certification framework), setting up resources and possible impact.												

	Continuous evaluation	certification	Invokes Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework for evaluation of the detected deviation
<p>Relevant sequence diagram/s</p>			
<p>Current TRL</p>	<p>Based on exiting tools/components (TRL 4/5), but the tool should be tuned for MEDINA’s needs</p>		
<p>Programming language</p>	<p>Java, Python</p>		
<p>License</p>	<p>closed</p>		
<p>WP and task</p>	<p>WP2 (T2.6) and WP4 (T4.4)</p>		

5.3.1.6 Orchestrator

<p>Component Name</p>	<p>Orchestrator</p>
<p>Main functionalities</p>	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide interfaces to the databases - Forward assessment results to the certificate evaluation - Forward assessment result hashes to the trustworthiness system
<p>Sub-components Description</p>	<p>The orchestrator mainly provides APIs to various components (see below). A dedicated subcomponent is the ledger client which transforms evidences and assessment results into the format required by the trustworthiness system and stores them on the ledger.</p>

Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any.	
	Interface name	Description
	Assessment results storage	An interface to provide assessment results which are then stored in the relevant database, and forwarded to the relevant components
	Database access	An interface that provides access to stored evidences and assessment results
	DLT storage	An interface to the DLT through which evidence and assessment result checksums are stored to the trustworthiness system.
	<i>TBD: Configure metrics and target values</i>	<i>TBD: An interface that provides access to metrics and target values</i>
Requirements Mapping	ECO.01, ECO.02, ECO.03	
Interaction with other components	Interfacing Component	Interface Description
	Assessment tools	Receives assessment results from assessment tools
	Databases	Stores and retrieves evidences/assessment results from the relevant databases
	Trustworthiness system	Sends assessment result hashes to the trustworthiness system
	<i>TBD: Metrics and target values repository</i>	<i>TBD: retrieves metrics and target values for the assessment components and offers an API to modify them</i>

Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant EG as Evidence Gathering participant AS as Assessment participant OR as Orchestrator participant EV as Evaluation (WP4) participant DLT as DLT participant DB as Database EG->>AS: register(toolId, monitorableMetrics, ...) EG->>OR: register(toolId, monitorableMetrics, ...) Note over EG: Continuous Gathering EG->>EG: start_monitoring(metrics) EG->>AS: post_evidence(evidence) AS->>AS: get_target_value(metrics) AS->>AS: assess_evidence(evidence, target_value) AS->>OR: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>EV: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>DLT: post_checks(checksum) OR->>DB: post_assessmentResult(assessmentResult) </pre>
Current TRL	From scratch
Programming language	To be decided
License	To be decided
WP and task	WP3: T3.1

5.3.1.7 Evidence trustworthiness management

Component Name	Evidence trustworthiness management
Main functionalities	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain an improved audit trail of evidences and assessment results. • Provide a record of information on a verifiable way (verification). • Provide a record of information on a permanent way (traceability). • Guarantee resistance to modification of stored data (integrity).
Sub-components Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blockchain dApp to be executed on the orchestrators for providing the information (evidences/assessment results) to be saved on the Blockchain. • Smart contract deployed on Blockchain nodes for information (evidences/assessment results) writing and reading operations as well as events generation indicating the provision of new information. • Monitor tool for subscription to the Blockchain based events and notification to the different monitors clients. • Graphical monitor client for gathering all the information saved on the Blockchain (and be able to check it, without needed any interaction with the Blockchain).

Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any. <table border="1" data-bbox="443 250 1348 757"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interface name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Blockchain dApp</td> <td>Provides the required information to be saved on the Blockchain. Provides a way to check the information saved on the Blockchain</td> <td>API REST</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Graphical Monitor</td> <td>Provides a graphical interface to check information saved on the Blockchain</td> <td>WEB</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Blockchain dApp	Provides the required information to be saved on the Blockchain. Provides a way to check the information saved on the Blockchain	API REST	Graphical Monitor	Provides a graphical interface to check information saved on the Blockchain	WEB
Interface name	Description	Interface technology								
Blockchain dApp	Provides the required information to be saved on the Blockchain. Provides a way to check the information saved on the Blockchain	API REST								
Graphical Monitor	Provides a graphical interface to check information saved on the Blockchain	WEB								
Requirements Mapping	ETM.01, ETM.02, ETM.03, ETM.04, ETM.05, ETM.06 OEGM.01, OEGM.02, OEGM.03, OEGM.04									
Interaction with other components	<table border="1" data-bbox="443 882 1348 1290"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interfacing Component</th> <th>Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Orchestrator</td> <td>The orchestrator will provide (and check, if needed) the information (evidences/assessment results) to be saved on the Blockchain by means of the Blockchain dApp interface.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Auditors</td> <td>The auditors will check the information saved on the Blockchain by means of the graphical monitor interface.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Orchestrator	The orchestrator will provide (and check, if needed) the information (evidences/assessment results) to be saved on the Blockchain by means of the Blockchain dApp interface.	Auditors	The auditors will check the information saved on the Blockchain by means of the graphical monitor interface.			
Interfacing Component	Interface Description									
Orchestrator	The orchestrator will provide (and check, if needed) the information (evidences/assessment results) to be saved on the Blockchain by means of the Blockchain dApp interface.									
Auditors	The auditors will check the information saved on the Blockchain by means of the graphical monitor interface.									
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant Orchestrator as Orchestrator_BC_app participant Network as Network_node participant Monitor participant MonitorClient participant Auditor Orchestrator->>Orchestrator: Normal previous Operation Note over Orchestrator: loop Note over Orchestrator: Repeat process n times Orchestrator->>Network: write_information(data) Network->>Monitor: Event write_information(organizationID) Monitor->>MonitorClient: create_topic_if_needed(organizationID) MonitorClient->>Monitor: subscribe_if_needed(organizationID) MonitorClient->>Monitor: Publish write_information(organizationID) MonitorClient->>Monitor: Notify write_information(organizationID) Monitor->>Auditor: Check information Note over Auditor: Auditor Auditor->>Orchestrator: Check information trust (if needed) Auditor->>Network: check_information(ID,current_hash) Network-->>Orchestrator: information_status </pre>									
Current TRL	Based on exiting tools (Brokel-Tecnalia)									
Programming language	Solidity, NodeJS									
License	Proprietary. Copyright by Tecnalia.									

WP and task	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP3 - T3.5 • WP4 - T4.2
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5.3.1.8 Evidence gathering tools

5.3.1.8.1 Wazuh

Component Name	Wazuh											
Main functionalities	<p>In general, Wazuh is a HIDS solution that provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malware and intrusion detection • Log data analysis • File integrity monitoring • Vulnerability detection • Configuration assessment • (Limited) monitoring of data about AWS & Azure infrastructure with simple compliance assessment <p>In MEDINA, Wazuh will be offered to the users as a tool to help CSPs satisfy compliance with certain EUCS controls as well as an evidence gathering tool.</p>											
Sub-components Description	<p>It is composed of a Wazuh server and Wazuh agents. The agents are deployed on the individual monitored machines and communicate information about the detected anomalies to the server.</p> <p>The server includes the Wazuh manager component along with the ELK (ElasticSearch, Logstash, Kibana) stack for gathering, storing, and display of data. Custom integrations are possible to send alerts from Wazuh to any external component.</p> <p>Agents communicate with the server using Rsyslog.</p> <p>Wazuh is plugged into MEDINA with the MEDINA connector component, which is responsible for extracting the data, relevant for MEDINA metrics, and transforming it into evidences, compatible with the security assessment component. It also includes two-way communication with the security assessment component (Clouditor).</p>											
Main logical Interfaces	<p>Include graphical interfaces if any.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left;"><i>Interface name</i></th> <th style="text-align: left;"><i>Description</i></th> <th style="text-align: left;"><i>Interface technology</i></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Wazuh WUI</td> <td>Main web UI</td> <td>Web, based on Kibana</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ElasticSearch</td> <td></td> <td>ElasticSearch HTTP API (REST)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			<i>Interface name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interface technology</i>	Wazuh WUI	Main web UI	Web, based on Kibana	ElasticSearch		ElasticSearch HTTP API (REST)
<i>Interface name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interface technology</i>										
Wazuh WUI	Main web UI	Web, based on Kibana										
ElasticSearch		ElasticSearch HTTP API (REST)										
Requirements Mapping	<p>TEGT.C.01, TEGT.C.02</p> <p>TEGT.S.01, TEGT.S.02</p>											

Interaction with other components	Interfacing Component	Interface Description
	Security Assessment component for Wazuh & VAT	Wazuh server (custom integration sub-component) pushes alerts to the security assessment component. Interface technology not defined yet (HTTP or AMQP).
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant EG as Evidence Gathering participant AS as Assessment participant OR as Orchestrator EG->>OR: register(toolId, monitorableFeatures, monitorableResources...) OR->>AS: register(toolId, monitorableMetricsIds, ...) AS->>EG: trigger_monitoring(features) AS->>OR: trigger_monitoring(metricsIds) Note over EG: Continuous Gathering EG->>EG: start_monitoring(features) EG->>AS: post_evidence(evidence) AS->>AS: get_target_value(metricId) AS->>AS: assess_evidence(evidence, target_value) AS->>OR: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>AS: post_asse AS->>EG: stop_monitoring(features) AS->>OR: stop_monitoring(metricsIds) </pre>	
Current TRL	Based on existing open source Wazuh platform: TRL 9. Connectors for integration with MEDINA to be developed.	
Programming language	C, Python, C++, Javascript	
License	Open source: GNU GPL v2	
WP and task	T3.2	

5.3.1.8.2 VAT

Component Name	Vulnerability Assessment Tool (VAT)
Main functionalities	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Detection of web vulnerabilities by running integrated vulnerability scanners to scan web applications (OWASP ZAP⁶, w3af⁷)

⁶ <https://owasp.org/www-project-zap/>

⁷ <http://w3af.org/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network reconnaissance (running hosts, open ports – exposed services) using integrated Nmap⁸ • Detection of vulnerable software (known vulnerable service versions) • Running custom scripts for detection of specific vulnerabilities • Scheduling repeating vulnerability scans <p>In MEDINA, VAT will be offered to the users as a tool to help CSPs satisfy compliance with certain EUCS controls as well as an evidence gathering tool.</p>									
<p>Sub-components Description</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scheduler: responsible for triggering scanning tasks according to the configured schedules • Docker interface: a component managing the connection with the Docker runtime, executing the tasks by running appropriate docker images and obtaining their results • Frontend: web UI management interface • RabbitMQ: connection between the subcomponents • VAT-genscan: integrating and orchestrating some vulnerability scanning tools and combining their results into a common report (based on Faraday CSCAN⁹) • MEDINA connector: a component responsible for extracting the data, relevant for MEDINA metrics, and transforming it into evidences, compatible with the security assessment component. It also includes two-way communication with the security assessment component (Clouditor). 									
<p>Main logical Interfaces</p>	<p>Include graphical interfaces if any.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="445 1099 1342 1435"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interface name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Scan reports output</td> <td>Pushing the results of scan tasks (vulnerability reports)</td> <td>RabbitMQ (AMQP), JSON</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Management UI</td> <td>Web UI to manage the scanning tasks and review their results</td> <td>Web</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Scan reports output	Pushing the results of scan tasks (vulnerability reports)	RabbitMQ (AMQP), JSON	Management UI	Web UI to manage the scanning tasks and review their results	Web
Interface name	Description	Interface technology								
Scan reports output	Pushing the results of scan tasks (vulnerability reports)	RabbitMQ (AMQP), JSON								
Management UI	Web UI to manage the scanning tasks and review their results	Web								
<p>Requirements Mapping</p>	<p>TEGT.C.01, TEGT.C.02</p> <p>TEGT.S.03, TEGT.S.04</p>									
<p>Interaction with other components</p>	<table border="1" data-bbox="445 1626 1355 1861"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interfacing Component</th> <th>Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Security Assessment component for Wazuh & VAT</td> <td>VAT pushes reports to the security assessment component. Interface technology not defined yet (HTTP or AMQP).</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Security Assessment component for Wazuh & VAT	VAT pushes reports to the security assessment component. Interface technology not defined yet (HTTP or AMQP).					
Interfacing Component	Interface Description									
Security Assessment component for Wazuh & VAT	VAT pushes reports to the security assessment component. Interface technology not defined yet (HTTP or AMQP).									

⁸ <https://nmap.org/>

⁹ <https://github.com/infobyte/faraday/tree/master/scripts/cscan>

<p>Relevant sequence diagram/s</p>	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant EG as Evidence Gathering participant AS as Assessment participant OR as Orchestrator EG->>EG: register(toolid, monitorableFeatures, monitorableResources...) AS->>AS: register(toolid, monitorableMetrics, ...) OR->>EG: -trigger_monitoring(features) OR->>AS: -trigger_monitoring(metrics) Note over EG: Continuous Gathering EG->>EG: start_monitoring(features) EG->>AS: -post_evidence(evidence) AS->>AS: get_target_value(metricid) AS->>AS: assess_evidence(evidence, target_value) AS->>OR: -post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>OR: post_asse EG->>OR: -stop_monitoring(features) AS->>OR: -stop_monitoring(metrics) </pre>
<p>Current TRL</p>	<p>Based on existing Vulnerability Assessment Tool component developed in the scope of H2020 CYBERWISER. To be extended, adapted, and integrated in the MEDINA workflow. Current TRL: 4.</p> <p>Integrated vulnerability scanners used are separately developed components by their respective owners. Their TRLs are higher (8-9).</p>
<p>Programming language</p>	<p>Go, node.js, Javascript, Python, Bash.</p>
<p>License</p>	<p>The VAT platform is proprietary, closed-source (developed by XLAB).</p> <p>Some sub-components and integrated vulnerability scanning tools are open source:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OWASP ZAP: Apache License • W3af: GNU GPL v2 • Nmap: Nmap Public Source License based on GNU GPL v2 • CSCAN framework to orchestrate scanners (part of Faraday): GNU GPL v3
<p>WP and task</p>	<p>T3.2</p>

5.3.1.8.3 Clouditor

<p>Component Name</p>	<p>Clouditor¹⁰</p>
<p>Main functionalities</p>	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence gathering - Assessment of evidences

¹⁰ Clouditor will be the component in charge of gathering some evidences and doing the assessment

Sub-components Description	The evidence gathering discovers resources in cloud systems, like Azure and AWS, via their standard APIs and forwards this information to the assessment. The assessment compares the received evidences against pre-defined metrics and their target values and forwards the results to the orchestrator.														
Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any. <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 25%;">Interface name</th> <th style="width: 45%;">Description</th> <th style="width: 30%;">Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Assessment interface</td> <td>An interface for providing evidences to be assessed against suitable metrics</td> <td>gRPC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UI</td> <td>A graphical user interface, e.g. for triggering discovery of resources</td> <td>REST</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Assessment interface	An interface for providing evidences to be assessed against suitable metrics	gRPC	UI	A graphical user interface, e.g. for triggering discovery of resources	REST
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Assessment interface	An interface for providing evidences to be assessed against suitable metrics	gRPC													
UI	A graphical user interface, e.g. for triggering discovery of resources	REST													
Requirements Mapping	TEGT.C.01, TEGT.C.02 TEGT.S.01, TEGT.S.02, TEGT.S.03, TEGT.S.04, TEGT.S.05														
Interaction with other components	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;">Interfacing Component</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Orchestrator</td> <td>Send assessment results</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>						Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Orchestrator	Send assessment results					
Interfacing Component	Interface Description														
Orchestrator	Send assessment results														
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant EG as Evidence Gathering participant AS as Assessment participant OR as Orchestrator participant WP4 as Evaluation (WP4) participant DLT as DLT participant DB as Database EG->>AS: register(boild, monitorableMetrics, ...) AS->>OR: register(boild, monitorableMetrics, ...) Note over EG: Continuous Gathering EG->>AS: start_monitoring(metrics) EG->>AS: post_evidence(evidence) AS->>AS: get_target_value(metrics) AS->>AS: assess_evidence(evidence, target_value) AS->>OR: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>WP4: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>DLT: post_checksum(checksum) OR->>DB: post_assessmentResult(assessmentResult) </pre>														
Current TRL	Based on existing tools/components: https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor														
Programming language	(to be defined) Go, Typescript														
License	Apache 2.0														
WP and task	WP3: T3.1, T3.2														

5.3.1.8.4 Codyze

Component Name	Codyze																				
Main functionalities	The component provides the following functionalities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Static code analysis - Validation of program specifications 																				
Sub-components Description	<p>MARK is a domain specific language to specify verifiable properties that source code must adhere to. It can for example restrict possible data values and their flow, or specify interactions between objects.</p> <p>The Codyze Plugin for Eclipse integrates the Codyze into Eclipse. The plugin controls the interactions between Eclipse and the Codyze analysis server and displays identified problems.</p> <p>The Codyze Plugin for Visual Studio integrates the Codyze into Visual Studio. The plugin controls the interactions between Visual Studio and the Codyze analysis server and displays identified problems.</p>																				
Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any. <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 20%;">Interface name</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Description</th> <th style="width: 30%;">Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Language Server</td> <td>Codyze provides an interface using LSP. It enables IDEs to submit files for analysis and receive analysis results for displaying in the IDE.</td> <td>LSP</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CLI</td> <td>Codyze provides a command line interface. It can be used to call Codyze to analyze a set of files and produce results. It is suitable for example for a CI/CD pipeline.</td> <td>stdin/stdout</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Interactive Console</td> <td>Codyze provides an interactive console with an interpreter (REPL). Files can be loaded and analysed. The resulting representation and detected errors can be interactively explored.</td> <td>Stdin/stdout REPL</td> </tr> <tr> <td>MARK</td> <td>MARK depends on Eclipse Xtext and reuses the UI elements of Eclipse and Xtext. Writing MARK requires an Eclipse IDE.</td> <td>UI of Eclipse</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Codyze Plugins</td> <td>The plugins integrate into the respective IDE and reuse their UI elements including highlighting and problem/error reporting.</td> <td>UI of respective IDE</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Language Server	Codyze provides an interface using LSP. It enables IDEs to submit files for analysis and receive analysis results for displaying in the IDE.	LSP	CLI	Codyze provides a command line interface. It can be used to call Codyze to analyze a set of files and produce results. It is suitable for example for a CI/CD pipeline.	stdin/stdout	Interactive Console	Codyze provides an interactive console with an interpreter (REPL). Files can be loaded and analysed. The resulting representation and detected errors can be interactively explored.	Stdin/stdout REPL	MARK	MARK depends on Eclipse Xtext and reuses the UI elements of Eclipse and Xtext. Writing MARK requires an Eclipse IDE.	UI of Eclipse	Codyze Plugins	The plugins integrate into the respective IDE and reuse their UI elements including highlighting and problem/error reporting.	UI of respective IDE
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Requirements Mapping	TEGT.C.01, TEGT.C.02 TEGT.S.06, TEGT.S.07, TEGT.S.08				
Interaction with other components	<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">Interfacing Component</td> <td style="width: 50%;">Interface Description</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Clouditor Assessment</td> <td>Send evidences</td> </tr> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Clouditor Assessment	Send evidences
Interfacing Component	Interface Description				
Clouditor Assessment	Send evidences				
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant CI/CD Pipeline participant Codyze participant Orchestrator Note over CI/CD Pipeline: Continuous Gathering CI/CD Pipeline->>Codyze: trigger(source_code) activate Codyze Codyze->>Codyze: analyze(source_code) Codyze->>Codyze: assess(evidence) deactivate Codyze Codyze->>Orchestrator: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) </pre>				
Current TRL					
Programming language	Java, Xtext				
License	Apache 2.0				
WP and task	WP3: T.3.3				

5.3.1.9 Organizational evidences gathering and processing

Component Name	Organizational evidences gathering and processing
Main functionalities	The component provides the following functionalities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gathering and processing organizational evidences • Providing evidences to the Clouditor for assessment
Sub-components Description	Organizational evidences are collected by examining the Repository of Documents. The processing part transforms these evidences in the form of technical evidences. These transformed evidences then are provided to the security assessment of the clouditor which can handle such technical evidences.

Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any.		
	Interface name	Description	Interface technology
	UI	GUI	REST
	Document input	This interface will allow to provide documents, e.g. an evacuation plan	REST/gRPC
Requirements Mapping	TEGT.C.01, TEGT.C.02 OEGM.01, OEGM.02, OEGM.03, OEGM.04		
Interaction with other components	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	
	Security assessment	Send collected evidences	
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant EG as Evidence Gathering participant AS as Assessment EG->>AS: register(toolId, monitorableFeatures, monitorableResources...) AS-->EG: trigger_monitoring(features) Note over EG: Continuous Gathering EG->>EG: start_monitoring(features) EG->>AS: post_evidence(evidence) AS-->EG: stop_monitoring(features) </pre>		
	Current TRL	From scratch	
Programming language	To be decided		
License	To be decided		

WP and task	WP3: T3.1
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5.3.1.10 Security assessment tool-Clouditor

Component Name	Clouditor ¹¹											
Main functionalities	The component provides the following functionalities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evidence gathering - Assessment of evidences 											
Sub-components Description	The evidence gathering discovers resources in cloud systems, like Azure and AWS, via their standard APIs and forwards this information to the assessment. The assessment compares the received evidences against pre-defined metrics and their target values and forwards the results to the orchestrator.											
Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any. <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 10px;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 25%;">Interface name</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Description</th> <th style="width: 25%;">Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Assessment interface</td> <td>An interface for providing evidences to be assessed against suitable metrics</td> <td>gRPC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UI</td> <td>A graphical user interface, e.g. for triggering discovery of resources</td> <td>REST</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Assessment interface	An interface for providing evidences to be assessed against suitable metrics	gRPC	UI	A graphical user interface, e.g. for triggering discovery of resources	REST
Interface name	Description	Interface technology										
Assessment interface	An interface for providing evidences to be assessed against suitable metrics	gRPC										
UI	A graphical user interface, e.g. for triggering discovery of resources	REST										
Requirements Mapping	EAT.01, EAT.02, EAT.03											
Interaction with other components	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; margin-top: 10px;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 50%;">Interfacing Component</th> <th style="width: 50%;">Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Orchestrator</td> <td>Send assessment results</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Orchestrator	Send assessment results					
Interfacing Component	Interface Description											
Orchestrator	Send assessment results											
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant EG as Evidence Gathering participant AS as Assessment participant OR as Orchestrator participant EV as Evaluation (WP4) participant DLT as DLT participant DA as Data EG->>AS: register(toolId, monitorableMetrics, ...) AS->>OR: register(toolId, monitorableMetrics, ...) ContinuousCameras->>EG: start_monitoring(metrics) EG->>AS: post_evidence(evidence) AS->>AS: get_target_value(metrics) AS->>AS: assess_evidence(evidence, target_value) AS->>OR: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>EV: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) OR->>DLT: post_checksum(checksum) OR->>DA: post_assessmentResult(assessmentResult) </pre>											

¹¹ Clouditor will be the component in charge of gathering some evidences and doing the assessment

Current TRL	Based on existing tools/components: https://github.com/clouditor/clouditor
Programming language	(to be defined) Go, Typescript
License	Apache 2.0
WP and task	WP3: T3.1, T3.2

5.3.1.11 Continuous certification evaluation

Component Name	Continuous certification evaluation		
Main functionalities	Evaluates the compliance level on all levels of the certification hierarchy (resources, requirements, controls, control groups, standard) based on the aggregation of assessment results and configuration (weights of individual tree nodes).		
Sub-components Description	Internal architecture not yet defined.		
Main logical Interfaces	Include graphical interfaces if any.		
	Interface name	Description	Interface technology
	Security assessment input	Receiving security assessments from the Orchestrator.	Not yet defined.
	Certification evaluation output	Sending evaluation results to storage and the risk assessment framework.	Not yet defined.
Requirements Mapping	CCCE.01, CCCE.02, CCCE.03, CCCE.04, CCCE.05, CCCE.06, CCCE.07		
Interaction with other components	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	
	Evidence orchestrator	Receiving assessment results	
	Automated certificate life management	Sending evaluation reports	
	<i>Component to be defined</i>	Receiving configuration for the evaluation of assessment tree: weights	

		of individual resources, metrics, requirements, controls, groups
	DSL Mapper	Receiving rules for the calculation of requirement fulfilment values based on the aggregation of assessment rules.
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant Orchestrator as Orchestrator (WP3) participant AS as Assessment Results Storage (WP3) participant CCE as Continuous Certification Evaluation participant CES as Certification Evaluation Storage Note over AS: Evaluation Initialization AS->>CCE: retrieve_assessment_results() CCE-->>AS: return(assessment_result_set) CCE->>CCE: evaluate_certification_state(assessment_result_set) CCE->>CES: store_evaluation_state(evaluation_tree) Note over CCE: Continuous Evaluation CCE->>AS: post_assessment_result(assessment_result) CCE->>CCE: evaluate_certification_state(assessment_result_set) CCE->>CES: store_evaluation_state(evaluation_tree) </pre>	
Current TRL	To be developed from scratch TRL 1-2	
Programming language	To be defined	
License	To be defined	
WP and task	T4.1	

5.3.1.12 Automated certificate life-cycle management

Component Name	Automated certificate life-cycle management
Main functionalities	<p>The component provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated the certificate states and assurance levels defined in the EUCS scheme based on the evaluation results. • Provides a tool for appropriate entities (CAB) to issue/update/revoke and sign security certifications for the cloud providers based on the updated certificate state. • Provides a tool for appropriate entities (CAB) to publish the certificate state in a public registry.
Sub-components Description	<p>If the certificate state is controlled in a Smart Contract:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blockchain App to be executed on the continuous evaluation module for providing the evaluation results needed to update the certificate state. • Smart contract deployed on Blockchain nodes for automatic update of the certificate state based on the evaluation results analysis and for the event generation when any certificate state changes. <p>Additionally:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event listener for subscription to the Blockchain based events and notification to the CAB. • Certificate signing application for the CAB to issue, update, or revoke security certificates to a CSP. • Application for the CAB to save the signed security certificates in a public registry. • Application for the CSPs to save the signed security certificates. • Application for the CSP to generate verifiable proofs based on the signed security certificates. 									
Main logical Interfaces	<p>Include graphical interfaces if any.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="448 607 1374 969"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interface name</th> <th>Description</th> <th>Interface technology</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Continuous Evaluation</td> <td>Provides the evaluation results to update the security certificate state.</td> <td>TBD</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CAB</td> <td>Sign and publicly publish security certifications</td> <td>Provided aaS.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interface name	Description	Interface technology	Continuous Evaluation	Provides the evaluation results to update the security certificate state.	TBD	CAB	Sign and publicly publish security certifications	Provided aaS.
Interface name	Description	Interface technology								
Continuous Evaluation	Provides the evaluation results to update the security certificate state.	TBD								
CAB	Sign and publicly publish security certifications	Provided aaS.								
Requirements Mapping	<p>List of requirements covered by this component</p> <p>ACLM.01, ACLM.02, ACLM.03, ACLM.04, ACLM.06, ACLM.07, ACLM.08</p>									
Interaction with other components	<table border="1" data-bbox="448 1099 1353 1458"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interfacing Component</th> <th>Interface Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Continuous Cloud Security Certification evaluation</td> <td>It will provide the evaluation results needed to update the certificate state.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CAB</td> <td>It will sign security certifications based on the certificate state. It will publish the certificate state in a public registry.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interfacing Component	Interface Description	Continuous Cloud Security Certification evaluation	It will provide the evaluation results needed to update the certificate state.	CAB	It will sign security certifications based on the certificate state. It will publish the certificate state in a public registry.			
Interfacing Component	Interface Description									
Continuous Cloud Security Certification evaluation	It will provide the evaluation results needed to update the certificate state.									
CAB	It will sign security certifications based on the certificate state. It will publish the certificate state in a public registry.									
Relevant sequence diagram/s	<pre> sequenceDiagram participant ER as Evaluation Results Module participant CS as Cert State Update participant CAB participant CSP as CloudServiceProvider participant PR as PublicRegistry participant Client ER->>ER: Internal Operation ER->>CS: CSP_ID, Evaluation Results, Major Deviations CS->>CS: Certificate state update CS->>CAB: Event (CSP, Certificate state update) CAB->>CSP: Generate security signed certificate CAB->>CSP: Save security signed certificate CAB->>PR: Security signed certificate CSP->>CSP: Security signed certificates local storage PR->>CSP: Compliance Request CSP->>PR: Compliance Response (presentation from signed certificate) Client->>Client: </pre>									
Current TRL	<p>Based on exiting tools (Identy Builder-Tecnalia)</p>									
Programming language	<p>To be decided</p>									

License	Proprietary. Copyright by TecNALIA.
WP and task	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• WP4 - T4.3

5.3.2 Other relevant components in MEDINA

The following descriptions correspond to components which are not part of the MEDINA architecture as such but need to be considered so that MEDINA Framework

5.3.2.1 MEDINA ontology: Ontology for Cloud Resources and Security Features

In the approach of gathering and assessing evidences for security certifications, there is a mapping to be made between the properties that shall be measured, e.g. an encryption property, and the respective gathering of adequate evidences, e.g. the development of a tool that can provide the necessary information about a cloud resource. Usually, these two elements have to be well aligned and have hard dependencies. We have developed an ontology that provides two essential taxonomies, one for cloud resources and one for security features, and defines relationships between them. This way, metrics can be defined for certain resource types and/or security features, while the evidence gathering can agnostically gather evidences for these abstract concepts as well. Thereafter, an assessment component can compare measured and expected values independently. We therefore reduce the dependencies that exist between evidence gathering tools and the definition of metrics. A further advantage of this approach is that new metrics can easily be added to the metrics catalogue. The cloud resource taxonomy defines a generic Resource at the top of the taxonomy. Below one child is, for instance, the Computing node which in turn has several child nodes, e.g. Virtual Machine and Function. The nodes along this hierarchy all can have (and inherit) relationships to the security features taxonomy which is structured based on the STRIDE goals. A Storage resource, for example, offers an *atRestEncryption* feature, as well as a Geolocation feature, inherited by the top node Resource.

5.3.2.2 CSP native evidence collection

At the time of writing, the “Evidence Collection/security Assessment CS level CSP-native component of the MEDINA architecture, has the objective of interfacing native Cloud Security Posture Management’s (CSPM2) assessment functionalities, to the MEDINA’s Orchestrator component. Contrary to the Cloudfitor component, which directly interacts with the rest of MEDINA’s architecture, basically all existing CSPMs [7] have their own (proprietary) API specification for consuming/providing data related to the continuous monitoring/assessment processes they implement. Therefore, a major challenge in MEDINA is developing CSPM-specific interfaces for allowing the Orchestrator to consume the assessment results and evidence gathered by native CSPM (e.g. Azure Security Center¹²). In our view, the main advantage of developing such CSPM-specific interfaces in the “Native Assessment “component, refers to facilitating early adopters to leverage MEDINA in their existing cloud ecosystems. Future sustainability actions in MEDINA will consider enabling a community of open source developers to create more CSPM-specific interfaces, in order to support additional public/private CSPs.

¹² <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/security-center/security-center-introduction>

6 MEDINA DevOps infrastructure and CI/CD and verification strategy

6.1 CI/CD Strategy

DevOps (short for Development and Operations) is an approach based on lean and agile principles in which business owners and the development, operations, and quality assurance departments collaborate to deliver software in a continuous manner that enables the business to seize market opportunities more quickly and reduce the time to include customer feedback [8].

“Develop and test against production-like systems” is one of the principles that stems from the DevOps concept *shift left*. The shift left concept moves operations earlier in the development life cycle. The goal of this principle is that it can be seen how the application behaves and performs well before it is ready for deployment, anticipating issues that are easier and less expensive to address earlier than in more advanced stages.

A required element to support the DevOps is to automate. Automation is essential to create processes that are iterative, frequent, repeatable, and reliable. Iterative process means that it can be represented by a well-defined series of steps; this enables the implementation of a repeatable process which is reproducible, consistent, and finally reliable. Only a reliable automated process can be used very frequently, with the assurance that it will not break. To apply these principles, organizations must create a so called “delivery pipeline” that allows for continuous, automated deployment and testing of reliable software artefacts. This is the “Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery pipeline” or “CI/CD pipeline” concept.

At an abstract level, a delivery pipeline is an automated process for releasing software from the version control system (e.g. GitLab) to the end users. Every change to the software goes through a multi-stage process on its way to being released. That process starts from building the software and is followed by the progress of these builds through multiple stages of testing and deployment. Continuous integration and continuous delivery allow to see and control the progress of each change as it moves, from version control through various sets of tests and deployments, to release to users.

Continuous Integration (CI) is the phase in the software development lifecycle where code from different developers is integrated together. This usually involves merging code (integration phase), building the application (build) and carrying out basic tests (test phase), all within an ephemeral environment. In the test phase, every element of the entire application is examined, from classes to functions. If a conflict is found between the new and existing code, the continuous integration helps to correct it.

The adoption of CI involves the introduction of some practices:

- **Use of version control:** every part of the project like source code, test cases, database definitions, build and deployment scripts, and anything else needed to create, install, run, and test the application must be checked into a single version control repository. A Version Control System (VCS) makes it possible to record the different revisions of the project artefacts, and allows to answer the question of who changed what and when, and permits, if necessary, to step back to revert unwanted changes;
- **Check-in regularly:** checking-in means submitting changes of software artefacts into the VCS. Doing this regularly brings lots of benefits: mistakes are easier to spot and correct; it is easy to revert to a recent known-good version if something goes wrong; it avoids altering too many files among versions.

- **Create a comprehensive automated test suite:** for frequent check-ins to work best, it is essential to have some level of automated testing to provide confidence that the application is actually working. There are three kinds of tests which are usually executed: unit tests, integration tests, and acceptance tests. *Unit tests* are meant to test the behavior of small pieces of the application (a method, a function or the interactions between a small set of them). *Integration tests* do the same but for several components of the application together, typically developed by different groups of people. *Acceptance tests* verify if the application meets the acceptance criteria decided by the business and is a formal phase in the software development lifecycle. These three sets of tests, combined, provide a high-level of confidence in the application.

CD can take several meanings. CD as **Continuous Delivery** automates the release of validated code into a repository (software artifacts). CD as **Continuous Deployment** automates the release of the app into production without waiting for the explicit approval of the developer. The goal of continuous delivery is to have a base code that is always ready to be deployed in a production environment. Continuous deployment means that the changes made by a developer can become active within minutes, provided it passes the automated testing phase. This allows receiving and integrating the feedback of the end users easier.

The **delivery pipeline** consists of the stages an application goes through from development to production. These stages may vary from one organization to another, and the level of automation also vary. Some organizations fully automate their delivery pipelines; others maintain manual checks and gates due to company requirements.

Typical stages of the **CI/CD pipeline** are the following (see next figure):

- **Develop:** In which developers write the source code and scripts. This stage includes tools for source control management, collaboration, and project planning. Tools in this stage are typically cross-platform and cross-technology.
- **Build:** The build stage is where the code is compiled/processed to create executable binary programs and where unit testing is performed.
- **Package repository:** A package repository (also referred as artefact repository) is a common storage mechanism for the binaries created during the build stage. These repositories also need to store the assets associated with the binaries to facilitate their deployment, such as configuration files, and deployment scripts.
- **Test:** A test stage is where development/testing teams do the quality testing and user acceptance. These tests include integration, functional, performance, and security tests. Automated tools are available for each of these types of tests. These tools are commonly integrated within a test asset management tool, that allows also to trace test results.
- **Release:** In this phase the final application artefacts are made available on a repository.
- **Deploy:** At this stage the code is deployed from the repository to the operating environment.

Figure 8. CI/CD pipeline.

6.1.1 Quality & Assurance

In our project, we will extend the DevOps approach by adding quality and security checks, hence we will talk about “SecDevOps”. The term reflects the fact that the role of quality and assurance (QA) in DevOps processes is increasingly important.

In traditional DevOps, a separate security team is responsible for security testing and its role is limited to the final phase. If the security team finds a security concern, the application must be corrected and go through the entire process again: this is not an agile principle and may cause a delay on the release.

Instead, SecDevOps means integrating application and infrastructure security early in the development lifecycle, and automating security control to prevent slowing down the DevOps workflow. Putting quality and assurance at the heart of the software lifecycle can actually save time, and can accelerate delivery and deployment.

In a SecDevOps approach, vulnerabilities are prevented and managed proactively. The Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP) [9] is a non-profit foundation dedicated to improving the security of software. OWASP is like a community in which everyone can participate and where all materials and information are free and available on the website. OWASP provides an online document called *OWASP Top 10* [10] where the top 10 most critical web application security risks are listed, and is updated every 2-3 years in accordance to advancements and changes in the application security market. The purpose of the document is to offer developers and web application security professionals, recommendations about the most prevalent security risks in order to adopt security practices that minimize the presence of these risks in applications. The risks are ranked and based on the frequency of discovered security defects, the severity of the vulnerabilities, and the magnitude of their potential impacts. OWASP’s importance lies in the actionable information it provides; it serves as a key checklist and web application development standard for many organizations. Integrating the Top 10 into the software development lifecycle (SDLC) demonstrates a commitment to improve secure development practices. For example, let’s take one of the risk from the list: *A9-Using Components with Known Vulnerabilities*; it states that applications and APIs using components with known vulnerabilities may undermine application defences and enable various attacks and impacts. This leads to use tools that verify security vulnerabilities in third parties’ dependencies, like OWASP Dependency-Check [10].

Instead of testing the entire product for gaps and bugs, each developer or team is encouraged to check the newly created code for such problems. Development teams can use code quality standards to evaluate the structural quality of software ahead of each release. By applying standards earlier in the software development lifecycle, a codebase can be developed further, or open sourced with greater confidence, resulting in less complexity. These measures are designed to be automated on source code through static analysis tools.

In an analogous way, the Consortium for Information & Software Quality (CISQ) developed Automated Source Code measurement standards for Reliability, Security, Performance, Efficiency and Maintainability, which were approved as OMG standards. Each code quality measure is comprised by a set of weaknesses in the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE). The CWE [11] is a reference point for developers and codifies over 900 known software weaknesses. The coding rules contained in CISQ standards [12] include CWEs as SQL Injection and Buffer Overflow. In fact, CISQ considers the security principle as one of the aspects of good software quality practices.

6.1.1 Containerization deployment model

Nowadays, modern applications are developed and packaged by following the concept of micro-services. This is an architectural software pattern that enables clear Application Programming Interfaces (API) to foster an easy integration among different application's components that are loosely coupled. Micro-services provide their functionalities as a service (like in a service-oriented architecture) and typically are specialised to perform a very specific job or task.

Micro-services are usually packaged in software containers, as the unit of deployment on a platform. A container is a lightweight form of virtualization at operating system level, where each container is isolated from the others, bundles all its needed software and libraries, and can communicate only through well-defined channels. Among its advantages, containerization allows building a reproducible software package, and this is why it successfully matches the principles of CI/CD and fits well for micro-services. An application, packaged in a container, behaves the same regardless the environment where it is deployed; avoids issues with operating system versions and tools that could hinder the smooth execution of the software; and eases a reproducible and secure deployment.

It is thus easy to understand that the **Package Repository** stage we described earlier could be fed with containers created for micro-services applications during the execution of the CI/CD pipeline.

Infrastructure as Code (IaC) refers to the fact that the environment in which the software runs should be software itself. Containers offer one such approach. In fact, developers can create the container descriptor file, that includes all the steps to package a micro-service in the container. This descriptor (software code) can be versioned and deployed according to the defined CI/CD pipeline stages. Containers allow fast and cost-effective scaling, can be secured more easily and can be quickly duplicated, reassembled or replaced. A container needs to be booted up on an already existing server structure or cloud service. In addition, one instance can be developed while the other is already running [13]. Docker containers are the most common implementation available today [14].

Since containers are packaged applications that includes many third-party tools, such as OS libraries and software, it is not uncommon to face security issues on these minimal OSs that are bundled along with the developed micro-service. For example, a micro-service written in Java needs a Java run-time execution environment, which in turns requires several libraries at operating system level: through this software chain, software bugs and security vulnerabilities can be nested or can be discovered as time goes by. Hence, hardening these so-called *container images* becomes imperative. Developers needs to be aware of known CVEs that affects some components before containers are deployed, reducing the overall risk profile. Furthermore, this needs to be iterative, since new vulnerabilities and bugs can be discovered over time, once the container image was designed. Some vendors provide CVE scanning tools for container images, which can be integrated as a stage in the CI/CD pipeline to assess the container security at every build.

6.2 Infrastructure in MEDINA Framework

In this section we describe the requirements and tools that are necessary to deliver an implementation of the MEDINA reference architecture, to be used by the Pilots.

We foresee three different environments in order to support this goal:

- **Development:** This environment is a collection of tools and services that can be used by the partners to create the components and modules of the framework. It includes

source code versioning systems, continuous integration and deployment tools, compilation toolchains, etc.

- **Testing:** This environment is where artefacts created in the development environment are integrated and tested. It could be unstable but provides always the latest available version of the MEDINA software.
- **Production:** It is a stable environment, where the components are deployed with a verified status of stability, but could not represent the latest version of the framework. It provides the MEDINA reference architecture to exercise the pilots use cases.

The figure below shows the three environments mapped to the CI/CD stages described in Section 6.1:

Figure 9. Three environments for MEDINA: development, test bed, production.

6.2.1 CI/CD supporting tools

In this section we describe the tools we intend to utilize with the aim to set up a continuous integration service following the CI/CD strategy we outlined in Section 6.1. The tools can be grouped in the following categories according to literature:

- **Version control system:** Version control, also known as source control, source code management, or revision control, is a mechanism for keeping multiple versions of software files, so that when a developer modifies a file s/he can still access the previous versions. These tools also provide mechanisms to people involved in software delivery to collaborate.
- **Build Automation system:** its first use is to convert the source code in a machine-understandable code that can be executed. All build tools have a common core in order to support build reproducibility: to model a dependency network (e.g. software libraries). A build tool must also ensure that for a given goal, each prerequisite must be executed exactly once. If a prerequisite is missed, the result of the build process will be wrong.
- **Artefact repository:** The outputs of the Build Automation system —reports and binaries— need to be stored somewhere for reuse in later stages of the CI/CD pipeline. That is, in the repository.
- **Continuous Integration software:** It is the orchestrator of the whole build process that integrates with all the other solutions and enables automation of the cycle. The orchestration goes through all stages, from fetching the code from the Revision Control system, through compiling it with the Build Automation, until storing it on the Artefact repository and evaluating the solution for quality and security issues.
- **Testing system:** Verify code changes through testing, preferably automated testing. This system supports the automation of both unit testing and integration testing.

- **Bug Tracking system:** It is a system to trace software defects or improvements that are found for the systems components in development and/or related to the deployment environments.

6.2.1.1 Analysis of CI/CD Tools

In this section, we evaluate a list of tools that could be selected for the building of the CI/CD pipeline in the MEDINA project and highlight their advantages and disadvantages in order to guide the final choice(s).

First of all, we have defined the methodology to search and select these tools. On one hand we have collected the tools from the MEDINA partners, listing the tools they provided or already knew; on the other hand, we have analyzed other tools in the market, attending to the requirements. All tools were grouped in classes by their role in the CI/CD pipeline.

The result of this survey was summarized in the NF requirements we proposed and agreed by the consortium, already described in the previous Section 4.2.1.

In addition, to improve the effectiveness of the analysis, we make use of a free instrument called OpenHub¹³, where we can find useful information about some key aspects of software tools like the license, the activity of community and the current or past vulnerabilities.

A license is typically permissive or not permissive. In the first case we can release software in an open source manner without copy-left; in the second case we cannot use it without copy-left, so it is more restrictive. Permissive licenses allow you to copy, modify, recombine, and redistribute the work with minimal restrictions. Copy-left requires that to release any derivative works done it is needed the same copy-left license. If you release a software library under a copy-left license like the GPL, and someone else wants to write a program using both your library and a proprietary library, they would not be allowed to do so. The purpose of GPL-like license is to force continuing the open source nature of the piece of software and its open development. On the other hand, the permissive licenses are preferred by the industrial partners, who need to protect their intellectual property resulting from software development. Some typical examples are Apache or BSD licenses.

The activity of the community is another important parameter to decide if a tool is good. If it has a lively community, measured by the number of commits in a month and the number of contributors, we can have a fair degree of confidence in that there would always be someone to fix bugs and improve the software overtime.

Regarding vulnerabilities tracking, that a tool presented a lot of vulnerabilities in the past is not necessarily a bad sign, especially if the owners were able to solve them and the community is big. On the contrary, can be a guarantee that there is an active development team and a particular focus on security.

To conclude, we can merge this information with the requirements already identified to have a more complete view for the selection of tools and decide which are more suitable for MEDINA development. We list next list of candidate tools in each class.

6.2.1.1.1 Code & Version Control systems

1. GitLab CE

¹³ <https://www.openhub.net/tools>

GitLab CE [15] is an open source software to collaborate on source code development. GitLab offers a git version control repository management, code reviews, issue tracking, activity feeds and wikis. Git is a distributed versioning tool, not necessarily with a single centralised repository, and for this reason it tends to be more complex for beginners with respect to centralised tools (e.g. Subversion). Apart from source code repository, it can be used for tracking software defects and enhancement thanks to its build-in issue tracking mechanism.

It is strongly established, and has a mature codebase maintained by a very large development team and few high vulnerabilities reported during the years as shown on OpenHub. It uses an open source MIT License that is commercially friendly.

2. Apache Subversion

Apache Subversion [16] is a full-featured version control system that boasts of a model, design, and interface that is said to be more advanced than other Code Versioning Systems (CVS). The open source revision control and software versioning platform's primary solutions include interactive conflict resolution, merge tracking, and file locking, with the most recent updates, containing features for path-based authorization, interactive resolvers, compression, and shelving.

CVS users attest to Subversion's centralized version control capabilities, which are said to be a reliable repository of valuable data and is easy enough to be learned and used even by those with only beginner's knowledge of software development. Subversion supports various types of users and projects, either individuals or enterprise-level organizations.

It is mostly written in C and uses the Apache License 2.0.

Analysis

Subversion adopts a centralized approach, while Git leverages on the distributed approach. This means that on Subversion there is a single repository where all developers commit their changes and retrieve updates. With Git, every repository can trace the changes and in fact every developer has a full Git repository on his or her development machine: typically, by convention, a repository hosted on a server is logically promoted in a way that developers push all their local changes which are there merged together. Git allows having multiple remote repositories, for example, a developer can push the changes to a public Git repository while pushing them also to his or her company internal Git repository.

As a result of their structure, Subversion tends to be easier to use for new developers, while Git has a steeper learning curve.

Subversion is usually used as the single tool, while Git is very frequently packaged in comprehensive environments that provides more than versioning only, like a well-structured web interface and other added-value services.

6.2.1.1.2 Build Automation system

1. Apache Maven

Maven is a build automation tool used primarily for Java projects. The Maven project is hosted by the Apache Software Foundation. Maven addresses two aspects of building software: how software is built, and how its dependencies are managed.

Maven provides a quite rigid model that makes customization difficult. It is based on an external DSL written in XML, which can be extended by writing code for plug-ins. Maven is, in its default

configuration, self-updating and downloads its own plugins from the Internet. This can be an advantage, but also a point of attention, since as a result we can have an unwanted upgrade of its plugins and we could hinder the process of reproduceable builds. Nevertheless, it manages software dependencies (e.g. third-party libraries) by automatically downloading them from the Maven Central repository over the Internet.

2. Gradle

Gradle is a build automation tool for multi-language software development. It controls the development process in the tasks of compilation and packaging, testing, deployment, and publishing. Supported languages include Java (and other Java-based languages like Kotlin, Groovy, and Scala), C/C++, and JavaScript. It supports a light DSL (not XML-based but based on the Groovy language) and manage software dependencies by automatically downloading them from the Internet.

Gradle is distributed as open source software under the Apache License 2.0 and was first released in 2007.

Analysis

About the user experience, a large number of users prefer to execute build operations through a command-line interface. For this, Gradle provides a modern CLI for this reason.

Both build systems provide built-in capability to resolve dependencies from configurable repositories. Both can cache dependencies locally and download them in parallel.

As a library consumer, Maven allows to override a dependency, but only by version. Gradle provides customizable dependency selection and substitution rules that can be declared once and handle unwanted dependencies project-wide. This substitution mechanism enables Gradle to build multiple source projects together to create composite builds.

Maven has few, built-in dependency scopes. There is no separation between unit and integration tests, for example. Gradle allows custom dependency scopes, which provides better-modelled and faster builds.

Maven is simpler to learn than Gradle and, being more mature, has a larger set of plugins for several needs [17] [18].

6.2.1.1.3 Artefact repository

1. Nexus

Nexus [19] is an open source repository that supports many artefact formats, including Java binary artefacts and Docker images. With the Nexus tool integration, pipelines in the CI/CD can publish and retrieve versioned components and their dependencies by using a central repository.

Nexus OSS has a broad support for many tools:

- Store and distribute Maven/Java, npm, Docker and more.
- Manage components from dev through delivery: binaries, containers, assemblies, etc.
- Advanced support for the Java Virtual Machine (JVM) ecosystem, including Gradle, Ant, Maven, and Ivy.
- Compatible with popular tools like Eclipse, IntelliJ, Jenkins, Puppet, Chef, Docker, and more.

Nexus OSS provides security features to centralise user accounts (e.g. on LDAP) and provides the capability to handle authorisations of users (or group of users, even LDAP groups) to the different archived artefacts.

2. JFrog Artifactory

JFrog Artifactory [20] is a scalable, universal, binary repository manager that automatically manages artefacts and dependencies throughout the application development and delivery process. Artifactory supports Kubernetes, the de facto orchestration tool in the industry, for automating deployment, scaling, and management of micro-services and containerized applications.

With the JFrog Artifactory it is possible to:

- Achieve a high availability with active/active clustering and multi-site replication for DevOps setup to support scaling.
- Release faster and automate CI/CD pipeline via powerful REST APIs.
- Deploy Artifactory as repository manager on-prem, in the cloud, or in a hybrid model.

Analysis

Both Nexus and Artifactory support integration with external authentication systems, like LDAP, which is a much-requested enterprise feature. However, Nexus has a quite difficult authorization mechanism to protect the different repositories, while Artifactory has a cleaner interface to allow assigning permissions to users and roles for protecting the access to the available repositories and individual paths.

The auditing mechanism provided by Artifactory seems to be easier to use, because there is a dedicated UI that allows seeing logins and accesses to the repositories. Nexus provides some of this information, but only through log files.

Both products support the setup of a Docker registry with virtual registry capability, which allows combining two or more Docker registries in a single registry. The web interface for Docker registry of Artifactory supports previewing the Dockerfile descriptor, while Nexus does not, and it seems more complete than that of Nexus also in regard to searching capabilities.

6.2.1.1.4 Continuous Integration software

1. Gitlab CI/CD

GitLab CI/CD is a free and self-hosted Continuous Integration server. GitLab CI/CD has a community edition and provides Git repository management, issue tracking, code reviews, wikis, and activity feeds. Companies can install GitLab CI/CD on-premise and can connect it with a corporate directory server (e.g. LDAP) for secure authorization and authentication. GitLab CI/CD is written in Ruby and Go and released under an MIT license. Since GitLab CI/CD provides Git repositories, the integration of the CI/CD pipelines are quite simple and straightforward.

2. Jenkins

Jenkins [21] is a Continuous Integration server, allowing to automatically monitor source code repositories, build software, run tests and deploying software. Through the installation of plugins, Jenkins integrates with a huge set of tools in the continuous integration and continuous delivery toolchain, including GitLab CE and JFrog Artifactory. It has several dashboards for controlling the status of the unit and integration tests (e.g. JUnit compatible) and dashboards

for visualising the status of the quality and security tests performed on code artefacts. Jenkins is made available via an open source MIT License and has a strong community of developers.

3. Tekton

Tekton [22] was originally part of the Knative project and is now under the umbrella of the Continuous Delivery Foundation. Tekton was released in 2018 under the Apache 2.0 license.

Tekton takes a modular approach to cloud-native CI/CD by implementing components that form the building blocks needed to create a complete CI/CD ecosystem. Due to its nature, Tekton is extremely powerful, and it provides the ability to customize entities which can then be shared and reused as needed.

A great advantage of Tekton is its modularity, which allows for componentization, standardization, and reusability within the CI/CD pipelines. The steps are operations in the CI/CD workflow that are executed in containers, and they are organized into tasks that run as pods on a container cluster orchestration engine (i.e. Kubernetes [23]). Tasks can be assembled and ordered within pipelines in any way needed [24].

Analysis

With the aid of GitLab CI/CD, it is possible to control Git repositories with total control over branches and several other facets to keep the code safe from sudden threats. However, in the Jenkins case, it is possible to control repositories but up to a few extents only. For example, it does not allow complete control over branches, but Jenkins supports many types of source code repositories others than Git, including Subversion.

In GitLab CI/CD, every single project has a tracker that will track problems and carry out code reviews to improve efficiency. On the other hand, Jenkins has a simple procedure for installation as well as configuration, and a huge set of plugins to integrate many different developers' tools. Jenkins is also able to automate non-software build pipelines (e.g. connect to machines to perform some tasks), while GitLab CI/CD cannot [25].

Tekton is the youngest project among those analyzed and it is specifically tailored to use containers as its running mechanism, which helps managing scalability. Pipelines building blocks can be factored and reused among different pipelines, fostering components reusability. Also, Jenkins provides the ability to create libraries where functionalities can be factored out and reused between different jobs.

6.2.1.1.5 Testing system (unit and integration)

1. JUnit

JUnit [26] is a mature unit testing framework for the Java programming language. JUnit is an open source (Eclipse Public License 1.0) framework used to write and run repeatable automated tests. It integrates with Jenkins for reporting the testing outcomes and with build tools such as Maven and Gradle for executing the tests.

2. TestNG

TestNG [27] is a testing framework for the Java programming language, inspired by JUnit and NUnit (for Microsoft .NET framework) and it is released under Apache 2.0. It is a testing framework designed to simplify a broad range of testing needs, from unit testing (testing a class in isolation of the others) to integration testing (testing entire systems made of several classes, several packages and even several external frameworks, such as application servers).

3. REST Assured

REST Assured [28] is a Java DSL framework for simplifying testing of REST based services. It supports all the different HTTP verbs (e.g. POST, GET, PUT, DELETE, OPTIONS, PATCH and HEAD) and can be used to validate and verify the response of these requests. Since RESTful services are used by micro-services API, this is a good candidate for testing such applications. REST Assured is released via the permissive Apache License 2.0.

Analysis

JUnit, in particular its version 4, is a very wide-spread tool, used by many Java developers. JUnit introduced a reporting testing format based on XML that has become recognized in many tools, including Jenkins, to represent the outcome of the testing activities. Such XML format has been also employed by tools other than Junit, as a testing framework for non-Java languages. TestNG also uses this XML format.

On the other hand, TestNG is not very used even if it provides some more features compared to JUnit. REST Assured, instead, is more focused on the definition of end-to-end test cases for RESTful web services: it uses a declarative way that uses the Java programming language. Since the MEDINA framework is being developed as a set of interacting micro-services, the use of the REST Assured framework is highly recommended.

6.2.1.1.6 Bug Tracking system

1. Gitlab Issues

Gitlab Issues is a free tool built into GitLab CE that makes it easier to track software development progress. It supports many of the same features as commercial competitors like Atlassian Jira [29], while being easier to use since it is integrated in the GitLab CE software. GitLab CE also provides an integrated Wiki platform. It uses the same license as GitLab CE.

2. Trac

Trac [30] is an enhanced wiki and issue tracking system for software development projects. Trac uses a minimalistic approach to web-based software project management. It provides an interface to Subversion and Git version control systems, an integrated Wiki and convenient reporting facilities. Trac provide an integrated Wiki system and a timeline showing all current and past project events in order, making the acquisition of an overview of the project and tracking progress easy. It is released under a BSD-like license.

3. Bugzilla

Bugzilla [31] is a robust and mature defect-tracking system. It allows teams of developers to effectively keep track of outstanding bugs, problems, issues, enhancements, and other change requests for the application being developed. Bugzilla is free software released under a Mozilla Public License.

Analysis

GitLab Issues is the ideal choice for those using GitLab CE for code versioning, since it is very well integrated. It is tied to each specific Git project, but you can report on groups of projects as well.

Trac is not a very sophisticated tool, but simple to use. However, Trac has a small community compared to GitLab CE users and developers.

Bugzilla is the oldest tool, once quite widespread, but with an old user interface and quite difficult to customize. Also, Bugzilla community does not release frequent updates and did not report many security issues over time.

6.2.1.2 *Quality and Assurance Tools*

The following section provides an analysis for the tools split between static code analysers and dynamic analysers. In static code analysis, we perform an off-line verification of the source code to spot both issues that affects software quality and security; this analysis works at the programming language level and software code descriptors (e.g. build files) in a white-box fashion.

On the contrary, dynamic analysis verifies on-line the piece of software when it is running on a compute node. This type of analysis can detect issues by considering the running software as a black box. It is useful to spot, for example, security attacks at application level like input validation problems. Testing of live RESTful web services falls into dynamic analysis testing, as well.

Since MEDINA is going to be developed as a micro-services application running on containers, in addition to the analysis described, we can consider specific testing activities for assessing the security of the containers that will run MEDINA: we refer to these further testing as container security.

STATIC CODE ANALYSIS TOOLS:

1. SpotBugs

SpotBugs [32] is a program which uses static analysis to look for bugs in Java code. It is free software, distributed with a GNU Lesser GPL. SpotBugs can be used standalone and through several integrations, including Maven and Gradle. It is extensible through plugins and the most popular for our purposes are *FindSecurityBugs* and *FindBugs Contrib*.

In particular, **FindSecurityBugs** is a plugin for security audits of Java web applications. It can detect more than a hundred different vulnerability types including Command Injection, XML Injection, SQL Injection, and Cryptography weaknesses [33].

2. SonarQube

SonarQube [34] is an open source tool for code quality and code security, distributed under GNU Lesser GPL. It performs source code reviews with static analysis to detect bugs, code smells, and security vulnerabilities on more than 20 programming languages, including Java, GO, and Typescript. SonarQube provides integration with Maven, Gradle and continuous integration tools like Jenkins.

3. OWASP Dependency-Check

OWASP Dependency-Check [35] is a Software Composition Analysis (SCA) tool that tries to detect well-known disclosed vulnerabilities contained within the dependencies of program. The tool extracts the Common Platform Enumeration (CPE) identifiers of the third-parties software libraries that the developed program depends on. It then uses such list to match against the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) public database to retrieve, when available, the correspondent security vulnerabilities. Dependency-Check integrates with Maven, Gradle, and Jenkins. It is released under the Apache Software License 2.0.

DYNAMIC CODE ANALYSIS TOOLS:

4. OWASP Zed Attack Proxy

OWASP ZAP [36] is one of the most popular open source tool for the dynamic analysis. A very active and mature community supports the project. OWASP ZAP supports a wide range of scripting languages (e.g. JavaScript, Ruby, Python, etc.). ZAP provides several functionalities like intercepting proxy, passive scanner, forced browsing and provides a REST API to interact programmatically with the tool. Using such API, ZAP can be integrated with continuous integration servers, like Jenkins, to programmatically start a security scan against a deployed and running software components. ZAP can be used to test both web sites by URL and RESTful web services methods. ZAP is release under an Apache 2.0 License.

CONTAINER SECURITY TOOLS:

5. Anchore

Anchore [37] is a scanning tool that inspects container images to unpack and analyze everything inside. It can be easily integrated into the CICD workflow thanks to its Jenkins plugin. During the pipeline, if the scanning of the container image doesn't meet the security requirements, it fails and returns back a report or an alert via webhook notification. It allows to detect both CVEs and customizable policy rules. It is released as an open source under the Apache license.

6. Clair

Clair is a popular open source container static vulnerability analyzer. It periodically collects data and stores them into a database. If a vulnerability is found, it produces alerts, reports or block release in production. It has an Apache license. Unfortunately, it does not provide integration with Jenkins.

7. Trivy

Trivy [38] is a tool that analyzes operating system packages and application dependencies in container images. It is easy to install, suitable for CICD and integrates with Jenkins in the latest versions. It produces reports about the vulnerabilities detected, illustrating for each library the CVE id and a CVSS score assigned. It is open source under an Apache license.

6.2.1.3 Selection of tools

In this table we can check what tool is in line with the corresponding requirements described in Section 4.2.1.

Table 7. List of tools with NF requirements' IDs.

	CICD.01	CICD.02	CICD.03	CICD.04	CICD.05	CICD.06	CICD.07	CICD.08	CICD.09	CICD.10	CICD.11	CICD.12
GitLab	√					√	√	√	√	√		
Subversion	√					√	√	√	√	√		
Maven		√				√	√	√				
Gradle		√				√	√	√				
Nexus						√	√	√				
Artifactory						√	√	√				

	CICD.01	CICD.02	CICD.03	CICD.04	CICD.05	CICD.06	CICD.07	CICD.08	CICD.09	CICD.10	CICD.11	CICD.12
GitLab CI/CD		√	√			√	√	√	√			
Jenkins		√	√		√	√	√	√	√			
Tekton		√	√			√	√	√	√			
JUnit			√			√	√	√				
TestNG			√			√	√	√				
RestAssured			√			√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Gitlab issues				√		√	√					
Trac				√		√	√					
Bugzilla				√		√	√					
SpotBugs						√		√				
SonarQube						√		√	√		√	√
OWASP ZAP						√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Anchore						√	√					
Clair						√	√					
Trivy						√	√					

The table below shows the selected tools for each class, including also the tools selected for implementing Q&A.

Table 8. Selected products for MEDINA project.

MEDINA – Software Development Tools	
Category	Tool
Collaborative Code & Version Control	Gitlab
Build Automation	Maven and Gradle
Artefact Repository	Artifactory
Continuous Integration	Jenkins
Testing	JUnit and REST Assured
Bug Tracking	Gitlab issues
Q&A - static code analysis	FindBugs and possibly SonarQube
Q&A - dynamic code analysis	OWASP ZAP
Q&A - container security	Anchore

6.2.2 Development and Testing Environment

The Development and Testing Environments run on VMs hosted by Tecnalía. These VMs are based on Ubuntu 20.04.

A dedicated VM hosts the CI/CD orchestration engine, the tools identified in *Table 7. List of tools with NF requirements' IDs.*, as well as the management of the containers cluster running the MEDINA components.

The CI/CD is reachable at: cicd.medina.esilab.org.

The Development and Testing Environments are implemented on a 3-node container cluster that virtualizes both environments making them independent and isolated. Such environments will run the MEDINA micro-services (containers) depending on their current maturity level: development will be highly unstable, while testing will host the reference implementation of MEDINA available for integration testing (a more stable codebase).

The resources available for the cluster are three VMs with the following settings, but thanks to the use of virtualization, higher resources can be easily allocated if deemed necessary:

- Memory: 8GB
- Cores: 8
- HDD: 120GB+200GB

Figure 10. Development and Testing Environments.

6.2.3 Production Environment/Resources

6.2.3.1 Fabasoft

The Fabasoft use case of the MEDINA project is deployed in the Fabasoft Cloud. In the Fabasoft Cloud, customers can choose where their data is stored and Fabasoft offers several European cloud locations. At each location, the data is stored synchronously in separate data centres. Data transfer as well as data storage is encrypted in the data centres. Fabasoft Cloud locations are currently available in Germany, Austria and Switzerland.

These provide Fabasoft with the necessary space, power and cooling. In addition, they establish the connection between the data centres and provide Internet routing. Platform-level

infrastructure for hosting, operating and expanding the cloud services is built, provided and maintained by Fabasoft itself. This ensures comprehensive control and enables Fabasoft to test and verify security controls at all levels. The Fabasoft Cloud Services are operated exclusively by Fabasoft.

6.2.3.2 *Bosch*

Bosch’s validation use case “European Certification of Multicloud backends for IoT solutions”, will be based on a multicloud deployment leveraging three public cloud service providers (i.e. Microsoft Azure, Amazon Web Services, and Fabasoft cloud). Deployed resources are operated by Bosch based on the cloud provider’s shared responsibility model.

At the moment of writing, the testbed will leverage resources from an IoT-related service from Bosch (to be further defined by WP6) deployed in both Azure and AWS. In addition, multi-cloud validation will be enhanced with the resources to be provided by the Fabasoft cloud (SaaS service model). In the case of Microsoft Azure, the Bosch tenant is located at *bosch.onmicrosoft.com*. For AWS will be used Bosch’s managed organization at the *bosch.com* domain.

7 Conclusions

This document contains an overview of the MEDINA Framework definition from different points of view. It explains the methodology for requirement elicitation, that combines a top-down approach (high-level requirements are elicited from what it is written in the Description of Action) and a bottom-up approach (proposed functionalities driven by the Use Cases in WP6).

The Use Cases of the MEDINA project, defined in detail in WP6, have been briefly described in the document, along with their specific requirements. The first use case, provided by the partner Bosch, is focused on the EUCS certification for high assurance, and will be based on a multicloud deployment (using Azure, AWS, and Fabasoft as public cloud service providers). The second use case is provided by the partner Fabasoft and builds around the real compliance activities regarding the Fabasoft Business Process Cloud.

On the basis of these analysis, an initial set of requirements—65 functional and 12 non-functional—are presented. Each requirement is presented using a simple form template, that contains Title, Description, Status, Priority, Related KR and Reference. An analysis of the requirements has been provided, where several matrices trace the coverage provided by the requirements to validate the use cases, the Key Results (KRs) or the components, as well as the requirements prioritization and status along the three expected versions of the MEDINA framework.

The initial architecture of the MEDINA framework has been outlined. The architectural framework is composed by thirteen components, that are described using component cards. These components will be instantiated by the use cases in WP6 and will be further detailed in upcoming versions of the deliverable. The components are grouped in well differentiated functionality groups (catalogues of TOMs/metrics/controls; NLP techniques/ontologies; risk assessment; certification lifecycle; organizational evidences; assessment of technical measures; evidence manager). To complement the architecture, the data model of the MEDINA framework is defined.

Finally, the Continuous Integration strategy to follow has been defined. Version control, regular check-ins and automated tests are the basis. The SecDevOps approach to integrate security early in the development cycle is presented. After a comparison of tools, a series of tools to develop the strategy is selected: GitLab, Maven, Jenkins, Artifactory. A containerized deployment model is foreseen to be used, and the development, integration and production environments are defined.

A second version of this document will be delivered at M24, containing updated versions of the architecture, requirements analysis and, in general, any related information that would be developed during the second year of the project.

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